

Creating a new future for port towns in the Irish sea basin, based on a deeper understanding of their past

PORTS, PAST AND PRESENT: CULTURAL CROSSINGS BETWEEN IRELAND AND WALES

Abridged Business Plan (for public display)

Priority Axis – 3 Cultural and Natural Resources and Heritage (with a focus on tourism)

Joint Beneficiaries: Aberystwyth University, University College Cork, University of Wales Trinity Saint David and Wexford County Council

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Executive Summary

The ultimate changes sought and the final outcomes for the project are:

- Coastal communities enjoy an increased awareness of their cultural heritage and develop new opportunities for heritage tourism.
- Port towns become 'stopping places' and 'spending places' rather than just 'through places' for tourists, with an increase in tourism-related employment
- Tourism Networks are formed between twinned Irish and Welsh ports, linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish Sea.

Specific Objective

There has been a movement of people between Ireland and Wales for thousands of years for reasons of trade, leisure, religious, political and family and also in times of war. Our countries have experienced shared histories and profound differences. Ports on both sides also share a history of absorbing migrant labour from other cultures and languages. The PPP operation explores the cultures of the port areas of Dublin, Rosslare, Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock and will bring this heritage to public awareness, both within coastal communities and to increase visitor numbers and enhance visitor experiences. In doing so it will increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

The project aims to bring life and colour to the ports, enhancing the experience of modern travellers of all ages and interests, and encouraging people to spend more time and money in these towns. It will do this by working with tourism stakeholders and local communities to make passing tourists aware of the deep history of these places. Specifically, the project teams will produce information in various formats, working with port authorities, transport carriers, tourism agencies, and local artists and writers to generate new tourism sites/sights/traffic, and commission creative works in the visual arts, literature and film. New audiences will be sought through digital technology including apps and social media. Irish and Welsh language material will be fully integrated throughout the project content.

PPP will help to make port towns, as a result of their rich cultural heritage, enriching places to visit. In doing so it will significantly develop new opportunities for heritage tourism based on enhanced use of cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

To achieve these objectives the project team will set up a series of tourism networks linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations, arts organisations, and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish sea – including a tourism web-forum, information sharing networks, and community events.

Implementation, changes sought and impact

The operation concerns 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation in linked cultural heritage tourism activities. Changes sought are to sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets. By raising awareness and fostering a renewed engagement with the past, the operation will increase capacity for community development of these heritage resources. It will also help to encourage tourists passing through port towns to make longer visits and to stop and spend time in these places of transit.

Outputs

- New tourism network, linking 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism.
- A broad range of media aimed to encourage tourists visiting coastal communities and port towns to spend more time and money.
- Creative outputs which engage tourists with the cultural heritage of these coastal communities.
- 2 FTEs in supported enterprises.

Activities to achieve results

- Research into the maritime and coastal history of the port towns
- Commissioning creative engagements with cultural heritage in order to shape lasting cultural legacies; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns
- Commissioning documentary films that showcase stories and voices from the coastal communities; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns
- Graphic displays of cultural heritage to be located in the ports
- Digital visualisations of past sea crossings and the history of the ports
- Community workshops that share and disseminate knowledge of

cultural heritage and improve skills relating to social media use in the promotion of heritage-related tourism

Evidence of Need

Ports play a vital role in the economy of Ireland and Wales, providing as they do employment while facilitating trade and creating vital lines of connection between and across borders. Many port towns are however sites of economic deprivation, places that visitors pass through rather than stop in. Coastal communities around port towns depend on the movement of people and goods but, as with visitors, tend not to be deeply aware of the histories and stories attached to the ports.

In both Ireland and Wales, Brexit is likely to have an impact on the geographies of mobility through ports. For example, there has also been a Welsh government committee report articulating concerns about the impact of Brexit on Welsh ports. This largely relates to questions around a hard border and customs infrastructure but the role of port towns remains under threat: <http://www.assembly.wales/laid%20documents/cr-ld11158/cr-ld11158-e.pdf>

With the exception of Dublin, the ports in the PPP Operation are sites of economic disadvantage. The 'Welsh Deprivation Index' (2014), shows that areas of two of our three port towns are some of the most deprived in Wales. Wexford has the 3rd highest rate of unemployed people in all local authorities in Ireland. The Wexford Local Economic and Community Plan states the need to further develop Rosslare Europort and articulates the benefit of maximising the presence of this significant port in the county.

While Wexford County Council regard the location of Rosslare Europort within the county as a major strength and a key access route into Ireland from Europe and the UK, there is also recognition that Rosslare itself is an area of economic need. Small Area statistics for the area around Rosslare Harbour based upon Census data for 2011 have been analysed by Pobal to give a Relative Deprivation score of -4.91. This score is based upon the demographic profile, social class composition and labour market situation of Small Areas in 2011. This is consistent with Co.Wexford as a whole (which has a 2011 score of -5.14) placing the area around the harbour as having a Relative Deprivation score that is *below average* for the country as a whole. Pobal noted commuter counties around the Greater Dublin Area (such as Co.Wexford) experienced the greatest decline in Deprivation Scores over the period 2006-2011.

Dublin Port is the largest and busiest Irish port in the Irish port sector. Dublin Port lies at the eastern edge of Dublin city. The percentage of the population over 65 years of age at 12.6% in the environs of Dublin Port is higher than the national average and the Greater Dublin Area. The population of the Dublin Port area is ageing faster than the national average. (*Report on the Socio-Economic Aspects of the Alexandra Basin Redevelopment Project*) and the Port is important as a large stable employer that provides employment and contributes to the social fabric of the area. Economic development plans for

Dublin Port have noted the need for cohesive social infrastructure. Better knowledge of shared cultural heritage can contribute to this aim.

Many economic indicators show that there is a considerable objective need to support economic development in *Wales as a whole*. In 2015, workplace Gross Value Added (GVA) for Wales was 71.0 per cent of the average for the total of all UK regions. Wales had the lowest level of GVA per head in the UK regions (Welsh Government 2017a: 15). Similarly, gross disposable household income (GDHI) in 2015 for Wales was £50.6 billion or £16,341 per head of population. This represented 85.5 per cent of the UK figure (Welsh Government 2017a: 15). Some of the Future Generations Indicators portray a situation in which Wales is seen to be lagging in economic terms behind other UK regions. The latest estimate of the employment rate for Wales from the Annual Population Survey (APS) of those aged 16-64 is 71.5 per cent for the year ending June 2017. The UK rate was 74.2 per cent for the year ending June 2017 (Welsh Government 2017a: 18).

Other indicators demonstrate the evident need for more sustainable and inclusive forms of economic development in *Wales' port communities*. The Welsh Deprivation Index (2014) shows that areas of two of our three port towns are some of the most deprived in Wales: two areas of Pembroke are in the top 4% of most deprived areas in Wales, one area of Holyhead is in the top 10% of most deprived areas, and a further three areas of Holyhead are in the top 15% of most deprived areas in Wales. Figures from 2005 show that these patterns are entrenched; there is an ongoing cycle of deprivation that characterises many of Wales' port communities (<http://wimd.wales.gov.uk/?lang=en>). Further evidence of the existence of poverty and deprivation comes from the fact that many of the port areas in Wales have been designated as Communities First Clusters (i.e. communities characterised by extensive poverty). A significant proportion of Holyhead forms part of the Isle of Anglesey Community First Cluster, while three communities (LSOAs) in Pembroke Dock (Central, Llanion 1 and Pennar 1) form part of Pembrokeshire's Communities First Cluster (<http://gov.wales/topics/people-and-communities/communities/communitiesfirst/clusters/?lang=en>).

Our discussions with stakeholders in the port communities have also testified to the existence of considerable concern about their long-term futures, particularly in Wales once the Communities First programme is terminated in 2018. The project will seek to promote a better touristic experience – and increase tourist spend – within these communities as a way of helping to ensure their long-term economic vitality. PPP will make the port towns more attractive places to live and work by working with key stakeholders and local communities, finding new ways to keep ferry passengers, cruise passengers and other tourists in the port towns themselves.

Headline details on the operation costs and co-financing package including the financial support requested from the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme.

Headline Operation Costs and co-financing

EXPENDITURE	€ TOTAL
Staff costs	2,368,296
Non-staff costs	525,989
15% flat rate	355,244
TOTAL €	3,249,529
Funded by:	
ERDF @ 80%	2,599,623
Indirect costs (For Indicating purposes only)	(355,244)
Match funding @ 20%	649,906
TOTAL €	3,249,529

Section 1 –Strategic Fit

PORTS, PAST AND PRESENT

1.1 Alignment with specific objective and targeting principles listed under the Ireland Wales 2014-2020 Programme and Priority

Aim:

Priority Axis 3 Cultural and Natural Resources and Heritage (with a focus on tourism),

Theme - Objective 6 Protecting the environment and promoting resource efficiency.

Specific Objective – 3 To sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets in increasing visitor numbers to coastal communities of the programme area.

The operation PPP is in clear alignment with the targeting principles and specific objective listed. PPP is a cross-border action between University College Cork (HEI), Aberystwyth University (HEI), the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies (HEI) and Wexford County Council (Local Government). The operation involves partnership across higher education and local government and brings in the participation of advisors and stakeholders.

In line with Priority 3 aims, the PPP will increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

PPP will create a new joint and shared future for port towns in the Irish sea basin, based on a deeper understanding of their past. The operation will explore, enhance and diversify the experience of travel between Ireland and Wales, drawing on academic research and community partnerships to open up new tourism opportunities between five port towns and their surrounding coastal communities on either side of the Irish Sea. The operation will turn ports from passage points into key tourist sites – improving tourism opportunities, tourist experiences, and the livelihoods of coastal communities. It will disseminate its results widely, develop models of good practice for coastal cultural heritage and create possibilities for future adaptation of its findings and practices.

PPP aligns with Priority Axis 3 Cultural and Natural Resources and Heritage (with a focus on tourism), which aims to sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets by increasing tourist engagements with port towns in the Programme area. The operation will convert tourists who pass through port towns into people who stop and engage with the specific cultures of the place. PPP will enable coastal communities around the ports to develop their tangible and intangible cultural heritage and mobilise their shared cross-border past as a driver to economic growth.

The operation PPP aligns with the views expressed in 'Getting cultural heritage to work for Europe', the report of the Horizon 2020 Expert Group on Cultural Heritage. The report promotes the economic benefits of cultural heritage while also making a positive case for the role cultural heritage can play in shaping social cohesion and promoting environmental sustainability.

There will be a positive impact on the well-being of those who live, work and visit the ports involved in the operation. Five sea ports in the cross-maritime area will be organized in a twinning pattern based on the current passenger routes:

- Rosslare and Fishguard
- Rosslare and Pembroke Dock
- Dublin and Holyhead

1.2 Cross-border Co-operation

PPP is a genuine cross-border operation in that it targets and addresses a shared cultural history that has been made across the Irish sea over time. Political borders have shifted over the centuries but the legacy of sea travel on the ports in the Irish sea basin is indisputable. The beneficiaries all share an interest in retelling this history in ways that will bring economic and social benefit to visitors and inhabitants alike. This is the first project to explore the features and impacts of this movement on the cultures of the port areas of Dublin, Rosslare, Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock and to bring this heritage to public awareness, both within coastal communities and to visitors.

External coherence. The operation will build on the results generated by other European programmes. With three HEIs as beneficiaries, the operation PPP is well connected to initiatives in H2020, including a current bid led by Prof John Brannigan and Prof Tas Crowe in UCD to develop an eco-system based methodology to measure the cultural value of coastlines. Other initiatives in the European research area are detailed below. Alignments with the 'sea basin driven' approach advocated in the Atlantic Area Strategy are strong.

Cross sectoral relevance is ensured via the combination of HEIs and local government as beneficiaries and a wide and varied group of stakeholders that include government agencies in Ireland and Wales, community and heritage groups,

The operation will make a renewed engagement with both cultural and natural heritage. This will act as the foundation of real economic benefits for the five 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation and exchanges. It will do this by creating a new tourism network, linking the five major ports and their surrounding coastal communities, under which three specific twinning link networks will operate. These twinning networks will ensure cross-border information sharing and cooperation between local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish Sea. It will further create 2 FTEs in supported enterprises.

Tourist numbers will be measured via annual port surveys with the initial survey used to create baseline information which will help shape future activities. Social media usage data will be used alongside Google Search Optimization information to track, measure and also drive uptake.

Joint Development

PPP has been jointly developed by the beneficiaries with a high degree of shared interest in experiences common across the sea. The operation will research, collect and display the cultural heritage of the port towns in ways that can be shared across the ports, adapted for future use, and form the basis for resilient tourism networks which can ensure cross-border cooperation beyond the project's lifetime.

Joint Implementation

Together, the beneficiaries possess complementary knowledge and experience and facilities in the area of cultural heritage. They offer added value in a cross-border approach to an operation that could not be meaningfully achieved on only one or other side of the border. It is only through joint implementation that a coherent approach to the cultural heritage of ports and their future role can be developed.

Joint Staffing

There will be continual sharing and exchange of staff experience while since cross-border working is key to the activities between and across the ports. All staff employed as part of the PPP operation will work across institutions and collaborate on the Work Packages, as well as working with coastal communities on both sides of the sea. Staff concerned with implementation and finance will remain regularly in touch via the Programme Board.

Joint Financing

Joint financing will be conducted via direct intervention based on ERDF / match funding from partners. The lead partner (University College Cork) is responsible for the coordination of financial disbursement to the individual partners. Each partner has financial reporting systems in place to ensure compliance with all regulations for the financing of the operation.

1.3 Alignment with the relevant Irish and Welsh Government Policies

European Relevant Policies

There are several European Policies that are relevant to PPP. Brief descriptions are given under particular policies which PPP will interact with in one way or another.

European Commission Communication *on A European Strategy for more Growth and Jobs in Coastal and Maritime Tourism* highlights the fact that coastal and maritime tourism is the largest maritime activity in Europe, is closely linked to other parts of the economy and attracts more than one third of all tourism business in Europe. Given the challenges facing the tourism sector in member states it is essential to address the cross-border challenges at EU level and promote cooperation and best practice sharing, including by promoting strategic trans-regional and trans-national partnerships of the kind promoted by PPP.

In order to overcome fragmentation at the national and international scale among tourism stakeholders, the **European Strategy for more Growth and Jobs in Coastal and Maritime Tourism** calls for closer cooperation among research institutes, museums, tourism companies and other stakeholders. Such co-operation should be promoted in order to develop innovative and sustainable products that respond to visitors' expectations and to support the development of trans-national and interregional partnerships, networks, clusters and smart specialisation strategies. PPP will achieve these via its relations with relevant stakeholders and through the Advisory Group.

The Strategy seeks to overcome geographical isolation and disadvantage in more remote and undeveloped regions through the development of tourism based upon cultural heritage, utilising national and regional strategies to ensure the coherence of tourism offers and better accessibility. The strategy also seeks to develop and promote innovative practices for regenerating and re-using existing maritime infrastructure.

A central vision outlined in the communication *Towards an integrated approach to cultural heritage for Europe* COM (2014 477 final) is that cultural heritage represents 'an irreplaceable repository of knowledge and a valuable resource for economic growth, employment and social cohesion.' As a shared resource and good, cultural heritage needs to be managed, protected and preserved in sustainable ways. Furthermore cultural heritage is both local and European, and is developed, shared and expressed across communities and borders. In short, *heritage is made up of local stories that together make the history of Europe*. For the Commission, a central means for the promotion and sustainable development of cultural heritage lies *in digitising cultural heritage, making it accessible online, and supporting its economic exploitation*. Doing this contributes to the aims of both the European Agenda for Culture and the Digital Agenda for Europe. PPP will advance these contributions by its use of mobile technologies.

The report *Getting cultural heritage to work for Europe* by the H2020 Expert Group on Cultural Heritage points to cultural heritage as a positive economic driver in the European economy; a key means by which to increase the participation of citizens in the governance and management of local communities; and as a means to ensure the sustainable development of rural and urban cultural landscapes.

Welsh Relevant Policies

Our project dovetails with a number of key policies and priorities being advocated by the Welsh Government and other related organisations:

The project complements the priorities of, and national indicators of progress used in, the *Wellbeing of Future Generations Act*. In particular, the project will help address some of the indicators that contribute to the goal of creating a prosperous Wales by increasing tourist spend in port communities (e.g. percentage of people in employment), as well as those indicators that relate to the goal of creating a Wales of cohesive communities by increasing the engagement of individuals and groups with their heritage (e.g. percentage who feel able to influence decisions affecting their local area, percentage of people satisfied with local area as a place to live) (Welsh Government 2016: 2; see also Welsh Government 2017b).

The project meshes effectively with the *economic strategies and policies* that have been adopted by the Welsh Government. The most recent economic development action plan *Prosperity for All: Economic Action Plan (2017)* draws attention to the important role played by the ‘foundation economy’ – or, in other words, sectors such as care, tourism, food, and retail – in promoting economic development (Welsh Government 2017c: 15). These sectors are deemed to be ‘the backbones of many local economies’ and, particularly in relation to tourism, ‘draw on opportunities that our unique historic and natural heritage provides’ (ibid). Our project contributes to this aim by encouraging the tourism sector to make more effective use of the historic heritage that characterises our port settlements.

Our project connects in a direct manner with the ongoing discussions taking place concerning city regions as new institutional and spatial vehicles for promoting economic development. Arguments have been made about the need to ensure that ‘areas on the periphery of City Regions should have their needs taken fully into account to ensure that benefits do not just accrue to the main city within City Deals’ (NAfW 2017a: 14). Specific comments have been made in relation to ‘the importance of spreading prosperity westwards in the proposed North Wales Deal’ (ibid: 14). This is an issue for each of the port communities that we will be working with since they are located in places distant from the cores of their respective city regions. Our project will help to counterbalance any potential tendency to foreground economic development opportunities in the cores of the new Swansea Bay and North Wales city regions.

There are strong connections between our project and various *tourism strategies* being developed within Wales. The Welsh Government’s (2013: 8) most recent tourism Strategy, for instance, seeks as part of its overall goals to grow tourism in a sustainable way so that it makes an increasing contribution to the economic, social and environmental well-being of Wales. An important strand within the Strategy revolves around a process of ‘place building’ or, in effect, ‘developing destinations that people want to visit and recommend’ and ‘providing opportunities for local communities to deliver memorable visitor experiences’ (ibid: 9). Our project contributes to this objective by seeking to change Wales’ port settlements from being merely points of passage to being touristic destinations in their own right. In a related context, our project also complements Visit Wales’ promotion of 2018 as the ‘Year of the Sea’

(<http://www.visitwales.com/sea>). Our project would help to bring a much-needed focus on port towns as part of this marketing initiative.

There is a need to consider the linkages between our project and ongoing attempts to *regenerate communities* in Wales (Welsh Government 2017d: 3): in this respect, '[t]argeted regeneration investment has a crucial part to play in widening prosperity and building resilient communities in all parts of Wales'. Our work with the three port communities has the potential to help in a process of enabling relevant authorities to designate them as 'regeneration areas' or, in other words, an area characterised by a 'complex range of challenges', consequently offering 'the opportunity to reverse decline with an appropriate mix of interventions over a finite period of investment' (ibid: 6). Significantly, seaside towns are viewed as being potential locations for regeneration areas. The project also relates indirectly to the Welsh Government's aim to increase the numbers of Welsh speakers in Wales to a total of one million by 2050. The Welsh Language Strategy (Welsh Government 2017e: 61-3) and most recent economic development action plan maintain that 'the future of our Welsh-speaking communities and our regional economy are linked. Thriving local economies will support our target of one million Welsh speakers by 2050' (Welsh Government 2017c: 21). Our work in Holyhead and Fishguard in particular will help the Welsh Government to achieve this ambitious aim in relation to the Welsh language. Our emphasis on making Welsh (and Irish) highly visible and audible in our creative and interpretive outputs will also increase visitor awareness of and interest in the multilingual nature of these areas, encouraging greater use of these languages within tourism infrastructures.

The Wales 'Year of the Sea' initiative draws attention to the value of the sea in terms of well-being and the economy. At the moment, it seems to offer very little focus on port towns, so PPP addresses an obvious gap in the Welsh Government focus on the sea.

Cruise tourism is worth £3 million annually to Wales and is increasing 33% per year, and the promotion of Cruise tourism is identified in the *Welsh Government Strategy for Tourism 2013-2020* as a key growth area, with the Framework Action Plan (Year 2)(2015) outlining the aim to 'increase the volume and value of cruise visits to Wales' by promoting the cruise ports, encouraging investment in port facilities, and providing a 'distinctive welcome to Wales'. This project will aim to work closely with Cruise Wales, which represents a partnership between the Welsh Government, ports, destinations and stakeholders who are all working together to offer an excellent cruise product for Wales. The project will help to enhance the capacity of the broader port towns (not just the ports) to receive cruise tourists, leading to the development of 'close-to-shore' excursions and port heritage excursions for tourists for whom longer shore excursions may be less appropriate (e.g. the physically impaired, frail, etc.). Such close-to-shore excursions will have the added benefit of having a lower carbon footprint due to the low (or zero) mileage required for transfers.

Finally, the National Assembly for Wales (NAfW 2017b: 14-16) have commissioned a report that examines the potential *impacts of Brexit* on Welsh ports. The report discusses the possible emergence of a hard border and customs infrastructure within Wales' ports and the potential for this to displace port traffic elsewhere. Such uncertainties reinforce the need to find different ways of continuing to attract tourists and others to use Wales' ports. Celebrating their distinctive heritage, we maintain, is one important way of achieving this aim.

Irish Relevant Policies

The UK and Irish Government's 'Evaluating the Value of the Economic Relationship between the UK and Ireland' (June 2013)

The Department of Transport, Tourism and Sport's policy up until 2025 (People Place and Policy) outlines the importance of developing socially, economically and environmentally sustainable tourism in order for Ireland to retain its competitiveness as a visitor destination. Alongside this the policy places cultural heritage as being of equal importance to Ireland's future tourism as its natural environment and landscape. The careful and sustainable management and exploitation of Ireland's cultural heritage for tourist purposes is hence of critical importance to its future Tourist policies. PPP will advance these aims by developing the tourist offering in Dublin Port and Rosslare, thus diversifying the range of offerings and lessening the chance of over-exploitation of renowned beauty spots.

PPP will help in the realisation of Failte Ireland's (the National Tourism Development Authority) strategic priorities to support a tourism sector that is profitable and achieves sustainable levels of growth and delivers jobs. As well as to facilitate communities to play an enhanced role in developing tourism in their locality, thereby strengthening and enriching local communities. The key strategic objectives of Failte Ireland's 'Ireland's Ancient East' Proposition include driving growth in international visitor numbers, tourism revenue and associated tourism employment in the regions which currently underperform in these areas. It seeks to move Ireland's east and south from a transit and day tripping zone to a destination which attracts international overnight visitors and differentiate the Ireland's East and South destination, within the international tourism marketplace, on the basis of the quality of its heritage experiences and a clear and memorable narrative. PPP will assist in reaching these objectives via its plans at Rosslare, which by offering a rich encounter with the history of travel in the cross-maritime area, helps to differentiate the tourist offering and encourage tourists to spend more time in the port.

PPP further contributes to the Department of Arts, Heritage, Regional, Rural and Gaeltacht Affairs key policy priorities outlined in Culture 2025 - Éire Ildánach: A Framework Policy to 2025 to harness cultural education opportunities through digital platforms by its use of innovative digital technology.

1.4 Alignment with the Atlantic Area Strategy

The Irish and Welsh coasts are both part of the Atlantic Area as defined by the EU. The operation PPP follows the AAS in adopting a 'sea basin driven' approach rather than one determined chiefly by geography or politics. The AAS is committed to the value of historic links between states and regions on all sides of the Atlantic and PPP investigates the history of such links but also provides an engaged and specific model of the ways in which such links can be framed and displayed in the present, for the economic and social good of both visitors to and residents of port communities.

What the AAS refers to as 'the Atlantic DNA: the geopolitical, geostrategic and geoeconomical reference layout of the Atlantic Area' is at the very core of this operation, which considers a deep cultural heritage shaped by time, whose meanings and resonances continue into the present.

The operation PPP can be seen to connect to the Research, development and innovation (R&DI) Action Strand. Such policies promote the knowledge-base of the Ocean as essential to the development of the maritime economy.

PPP expresses the added value outcomes for each stakeholder across a range of common priorities within the Atlantic Area Strategy and aligns with its aim to take full advantage of the Atlantic potential for the benefit of the EU as a whole. It does so in particular by:

- Expressing an awareness of common challenges between and across the port towns in the Irish Sea basin
- Developing a coherent expression of shared cultural heritage that takes into account transversal relationships over time
- Stimulating economic development in the Atlantic area in particular in relation to ports
- Improving the competitiveness and sustainability of tourism
- Engaging with the ferry companies whose role in the economic uses and exploitation of the ocean make them a key player in the Atlantic Area

1.5 Outline of Cross Cutting Themes of Equal Opportunities and Environmental Sustainability

PPP will undertake continuous monitoring of its activities to ensure that the monitoring and evaluation criteria are in compliance with all policies and procedures. The operation will be evaluated with reports being published on its website.

Sustainable development

PPP will ensure sustainable development is a key element in the operation. Each of the beneficiaries is committed to embedding wider sustainable thinking into decision-making processes and this will fully inform the PPP operation.

Lead beneficiary **UCC** is committed to a journey towards sustainability. In 2007 the university became the first in the world to be awarded a Green Flag from the Foundation of Environmental Education. UCC renewed its Green Flag in 2013 and 2016, and in July 2016 published its Sustainability Strategy committing to be a 'world-class University leading the drive towards sustainability in Higher Education Institutes and beyond, to our community, region and planet.' UCC's Green Campus includes a university-wide module on sustainability, and is student-led, research-informed and practice-focused, demonstrating a strong commitment across all levels and divisions in the university. The university is finding ways to reduce the negative impacts of its purchasing decisions by implementing green or sustainable procurement policies and processes. These will be fully integrated into the PPP operation.

Aberystwyth University has been awarded EcoCampus Gold Award following an independent audit of its environmental management system. The award recognises the University's commitment to improving its environment and sustainability, and paves the way for securing the EcoCampus Platinum Award and the internationally accredited ISO14001 environment standard.

The **University of Wales Trinity St David** has published its key strategies and policies related to sustainability here:

<http://www.uwtsd.ac.uk/sustainability/strategies-and-policies/>

University of Wales Trinity Saint David recognises that environmental issues are fundamental to the future health and well-being of all those involved with our institution, the wider community and our planet. Thus the University is committed to providing a stimulating, progressive and sustainable environment of learning, including full consideration of social, economic and environmental impacts and opportunities. The University accepts its responsibility of demonstrating leadership in sustainability through innovation and enhancement of its actions as an institution at the local, regional and global levels, minimising our impacts and determining sustainable solutions to environmental concerns. These principles will be fully integrated into the PPP operation

PPP will contribute to meeting well-being targets established by both the Irish and Welsh governments. It will contribute to resilience as the activities proposed seek to ensure a 'natural environment with healthy functioning ecosystems that support social, economic and ecological resilience and the capacity to adapt to change'

Equal opportunities and non-discrimination

PPP will promote greater awareness and understanding of the important roles that women have played, and continue to play, in coastal communities. Research will be conducted with a view to recovering the role of both women and men in the history of the cross-maritime area. The understated role of women in fisheries was highlighted during the Irish Sea symposium with the rather pointed comment that there appears to be little interest in researching this largely undiscovered topic. Women have played a key role in maritime

communities for centuries but are not always evident in visualisations of the maritime past. PPP will address and make visible the significant social and economic contribution of women to the cross-maritime area across time. Workshops will be organised with a view to full representation of both women and men and gender balance will also be a concern in organising the practicalities of workshop discussions.

Lead beneficiary **UCC** has strong measures in place to address gender equality in the workplace and to ensure that gender equality is an essential part of research design and delivery. UCC currently holds an Athena Swan Bronze award and its UCC Athena SWAN Action Plan 2016-2019 may be viewed here: <https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/aboutucc/presidentx27soffice/athenaswan/ACTIONPLAN.pdf>

UCC is currently implementing GENOVATE's Gender Equality Action plan which includes nine gender equality actions, eight of which the University Management Team committed to implementing at its meeting on the 17 September 2015, and the action 1b on 8 March 2017.

The nine actions are complemented and reinforced by [tools](#) for supporting implementation. Both the actions and the tools are informed by the following:

- (i) an intra-organisational investigation—or gender equality assessment—of policy and practice;
- (ii) the technical knowledge and expertise of [cross-European GENOVATE Consortium](#) partners; and
- (iii) a rigorous review and analysis of international policy and practice.

Lead beneficiary UCC guarantees equal opportunities and non-discrimination to all its employees. As a matter of legislation and as a matter of University policy, UCC provides equal opportunities to all employees and applicants for employment in access to employment, conditions of employment, training or experience for or in relation to employment, promotion or re-grading, or classification of job, and in other employment decisions without discrimination on grounds of gender, marital status, family status, sexual orientation, religion, age, disability, race or membership of the Traveller community. This code of practice affects research conducted by the University also and will determine both policy and practice for the PPP operation.

Aberystwyth University's procedures in relation to Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming will further inform the operation. The project will meet all UK statutory obligations under relevant legislation by complying with Aberystwyth University's Equal Opportunities and Diversity Policy. The University's policy is guided by the Equal Pay Act, Sex Discrimination Act, Race Relations Acts, Disability Discrimination Act (1995), Special Educational Needs and Disability Act (2001), Human Rights Act (1998) and the EU Equal Treatment Framework Directive (2000/78). In addition, the project will adhere to the Codes of Practice issued by the Commission for Equality and Human Rights.

It is recognised that a diverse workforce brings strong benefits to an organisation, and such diversity will be sought in line with Aberystwyth University recruitment policies, including those regarding internal and external advertisement of vacancies. Aberystwyth University is committed to gender equality and increasing the number of women in science and technology, demonstrated by its recent achievement of an Athena Swan Bronze Award and Gender Equality Charter Mark (GEM) Bronze award.

The **University of Wales Trinity Saint David** has articulated the values of equality and diversity and is working towards identifying and combatting all forms of discrimination. The University of Wales Trinity Saint David Strategic Equality Plan is available at <https://www.uwtsd.ac.uk/media/uwtsd-website/content-assets/documents/strategies-policies/strategic-plan-equality-2016-2020.pdf>

Wexford County Council are committed to creating and maintaining a business and working environment that encourages and supports the right to dignity and respect for all. Anyone who works in or deals with the Wexford Local Authorities is expected to treat every individual with dignity and respect. All will be treated equally and respected for their individuality and diversity. The Council's Equal Status Policy outlines the commitment of the Wexford Local Authorities to meet our obligations under the Equal Status Acts 2000 to 2004, to be proactive in the promotion of equality and to work towards the prevention of discrimination.

Building on these institutional policies and commitments, PPP will treat all stakeholders equally and fairly while recognising individual or group diversity and needs and adapting the operation, where possible. All stakeholders will be afforded equality of access. PPP will achieve real equality of opportunity by continuously monitoring their policies, practices and procedures to ensure that they do not perpetuate any existing inequalities that may apply.

1.6 Planned or potential opportunities for integration with other European Structural and Investment (ESI) funding programmes, such as ERDF, ESF, EAFRD (Rural Development) or EMFF (Fisheries Fund).

European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)

This fund, which includes the Interreg programmes, aims to strengthen economic and social cohesion between its poorer regions by co-financing investments in actions that will stimulate economic development and create jobs.

The partner beneficiaries have been involved with several ERDF operations including *Aberystwyth Innovation and Enterprise Campus (AIEC)*, *BEACON (and BEACON +)*, *VetHub 1*, *GEOM*, and *Future Food* and is currently developing three new proposed operations. All of these aim to contribute to the

regional economy and to create new jobs though none appear to have any direct synergies with *Ports – Past and Present*.

There are clear synergies between PPP and a number of currently or recently funded ERDF programmes:

i) We will ensure that PPP meshes with two of the three routes defined as part of the ERDF-funded scheme, *The Wales Way*. There are clear opportunities to ensure that the heritage of Fishguard can feature as part of The Coastal Way, the tourist route that stretches from Aberdaron to St David's. Similarly, Holyhead represents the start or end point of The North Wales way and we envisage much potential in promoting its heritage as part of this walking experience along the North Wales coast.

ii) The £37m Sustainable and Coastal Tourism Projects funded by the 2007-2013 ERDF Programme focus on developing a series of tourist centres of excellence along the coast of Wales. While not a centre of excellence, PPP will enable us to add value to the tourist experience in Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock.

iii) PPP will complement the £12m that has been invested in the development of the Wales Coastal Path. The promotion of heritage tourism within the three ports will help to ensure that these are more likely to become 'stopping places' rather than 'through places' for walkers traversing the coastal path.

iv) PPP meshes well with CADW's Pan Wales Interpretation Plan, which has been developed to add depth and authenticity to Wales' heritage product. It also has the potential to contribute to CADW's Heritage Tourism project, which seeks to support developments at key cultural and heritage sites across West Wales and the Valleys. We will work with CADW to seek to ensure that the three port become recognised as important heritage sites in their own right.

European Social Fund (ESF)

The priorities of the Operational Programme for the European Social Fund in West Wales and the Valleys and of Ireland's Programme for Employability, Inclusion and Learning (PEIL) focus upon alleviating poverty, social exclusion and inequality through the provision of skills and sustainable employment opportunities.

Aberystwyth University is, and has been, involved with several ESF operations including the *Knowledge Exchange Skills Scholarship (KESS)* and is currently developing two new operations *Tri Sci Cymru* (a science outreach programme) and *Welsh BioInnovation*. The aim of *Welsh BioInnovation* is to provide a framework of training for Aberystwyth and Swansea universities to work with biotech and food companies in West Wales and the Valleys to enhance their workforce's ability to: recognise innovation as a route to market; facilitate innovation as a way of working; and manage innovation within their workplaces.

European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)

A priority (4A) of the Rural Development Programme (RDP) for Wales is restoring, preserving and enhancing biodiversity, including in Natura 2000 areas, and in areas facing natural or other specific constraints. Actions arising from this priority include landscape scale action towards conserving and enhancing Wales's native wildlife & biodiversity (4.2.18) and managing and protecting landscape and the historic environment while improving access (4.2.19). Also to protect and preserve an important and ancient part of the agricultural landscape, mediating the impacts of coastal processes on the land, providing habitats for wildlife and access for tourists. PPP's creative engagements (outlined in WP2) will include an environmental strand using nature writing, art and photography to engage habitat creation and protection.

European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF)

The EMFF Operation Programmes for the UK and Ireland share priorities aimed at promoting environmentally sustainable, resource efficient, innovative, competitive and knowledge-based fisheries (Union Priority 1) and aquaculture (Union Priority 2). Included in these priorities is the protection of biodiversity in marine species and habitats through collaboration between the fisheries and aquaculture sectors and marine scientists. Non-native species are recognised as a threat to biodiversity that needs to be monitored, reported and managed. The 'Seafood Development Plan 2014 - 2020+' is Ireland's Operational Plan to implement this EU regulation. Although *Ports – Past and Present* is not concerned specifically with fisheries or aquaculture, all measures aimed at improving coastal enterprises and biodiversity will contribute towards the regeneration of coastal communities and could encourage visitors to stay longer in the port towns.

Other Ireland-Wales Programme 2014-2020 operations

Priority 2

Ecostructure

This operation will raise awareness of eco-engineering solutions to the challenge of coastal adaptation to climate change by providing developers and regulators with accessible tools and resources, based on interdisciplinary research in the fields of ecology, engineering and socioeconomics.

Ecostructure aims to promote the incorporation of secondary ecological and societal benefits into coastal defence and renewable energy structures, with benefits to the environment, to coastal communities and to the blue and green sectors of the Irish and Welsh economies. There is no direct synergy anticipated with this operation but if opportunities arise to add value to either or both operations this will be explored.

ACCLIMATISE

This operation focusses upon the impacts of climate change on water quality. Synergies with *Ports – Past and Present* are considered unlikely to arise.

CHERISH

This operation addresses the impacts of climate change upon the cultural heritage of reefs, islands and headlands. Any opportunity for adding value to each operation will be identified and acted upon.

BLUEFISH

The focus of this operation is upon the impacts of climate change on fisheries and aquaculture in the Irish Sea. Synergies with *Ports – Past and Present* is considered unlikely at this stage.

Other Priority 3 operations new or under development

PPP will explore any potential opportunities for integrating with other PA 3 projects. These include:

Legendary Celtic Coasts

The proposed operation aims to identify, characterise and promote links between popular myths, prose, and poetry, and natural and cultural coastal landscape features, focusing on examples where connections exist across the Irish Sea. Myths include the Mabinogion tales and Arthurian legends, and more recent folklore such as the Lamma Flood/Llif Coch Awst that connects coastal mid Wales and southeast Ireland. The aim is to increase visitor numbers (including holiday makers, school/university groups, and the differently abled) to economically-deprived parts of coastal west Wales and southeast Ireland by developing and marketing new, community-led, tourist networks and products (e.g. trails, apps, websites, crafts, art commissions).

The team developing *Legendary Celtic Coasts* is in close dialogue with those developing the *Ports Past and Present* operation and while there is no overlap in the precise geographical areas targeted it is anticipated that there will be opportunities for adding value to each operation, particularly through promotion and marketing.

Celtic Routes

This recently approved operation works to establish an innovative and penetrative cross border complementary tourism campaign leveraging economies of scale. It offers a coherent, integrated, efficient and sustainable promotional campaign, which can be effectively sustained. The development of innovative content will provide Ireland and Wales with new digital content, editorial, eye catching imagery and innovative video footage to use across all digital and social platforms. This would materialise as a coherent, integrated and efficient promotional campaign leading to an extending of the season. The project will also create a unique, discreet and competitive destination attracting and creating new and exciting opportunities for first time visitors.

The proposed operation will focus on the following coastal communities:

Wales:

- Carmarthenshire
- Pembrokeshire
- Ceredigion

Ireland

- Waterford
- Wexford
- Wicklow

This operation has potential for synergy with *Ports – Past and Present* in Pembrokeshire. To ensure that the two operations can maximise opportunities for synergy and added value, it is proposed that *Ports – Past and Present* will invite a representative of *Celtic Routes* onto its Advisory Group.

Rediscovering Ancient Connections - The Saints

A project between Pembrokeshire County Council and Wexford County Council, *Rediscovering Ancient Connections* is particular to the areas of Ferns, Co Wexford (where Saint Aidan had a monastery) and Saint David's in Wales and is centred around the communities within each. It features a mentoring element between the two within a business and community context. Although different in its scope, deliverables and geography, this operation has potential for synergy with *Ports – Past and Present*. Good contact is ensured between the two projects via the shared role of Wexford County Council. It is anticipated that there will be some opportunities for adding value to each operation, particularly through promotion and marketing.

1.7 Planned or potential integration with other EU funding streams such as Transnational and Interregional programmes, or the Horizon 2020 or LIFE+ programmes.

There are a number of transnational/interregional programmes within the current 2014-2020 funding cycle and some have been noted above.

A number of activities are taking place as part of the EU European Year of Cultural Heritage in 2018 and every effort will be made to engage with these events and resulting projects:

H2020 Innovation and Cultural Heritage Conference March 2018

The high-level Horizon 2020 conference – organised by the European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation.

The conference is part of the programme of the European Year of Cultural Heritage and will contribute to its legacy by launching the public discussion about the objectives of European research and innovation policy for Cultural Heritage beyond 2020. H2020 Research and Innovation policy states that 'European Cultural Heritage contributes to people's well-being, as well as to social cohesion, inclusion and openness towards a multicultural society. For this reason access to and sharing of Cultural Heritage must be improved by research and innovation.' It can be anticipated that further H2020 projects will be funded in this area and the PPP operation will use existing academic connections and networks to explore links and synergies as appropriate.

In addition, UCD are currently Lead Partners on a H2020 bid for a project that advances an interdisciplinary (STEM/Humanities) investigation of applying an ecosystem services model to the study of coastal communities. PPP has good connections with the UCD PI and, should this bid be successful, we will connect up our endeavours.

1.8 Evidence of Engagement with all potential joint beneficiaries and stakeholders in shaping of the proposal.

Letters of support from stakeholders form part of the Annex to this document.

Table 1. Engagement with Joint Beneficiaries

Personnel key: [Redacted]

Institution key: Cork U - Cork University; AU – Aberystwyth University;
CAWCS – Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies; Wexford = Wexford
County Council

Letter of support already obtained: (Letter)

Table 1. Engagement with Joint Beneficiaries

Personnel key: [Redacted]

Institution key: Cork U – University College Cork; AU – Aberystwyth University;
CAWCS – Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies; Wexford = Wexford
County Council

Letter of support already obtained: (Letter)

Date	Attendees	Summary
21/3/17	[Redacted] (AU)	Project planning. Meeting. Aberystwyth
28/3/17	[Redacted] (AU)	Project planning. Meeting. Aberystwyth
4/17	[Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (Cork U)	Email contacts establishing basis of AU, Cork U common interests in project.
24/5/17	[Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (CAWCS)	Project planning. Meeting. Aberystwyth. This meeting forged a partnership between the two Wales beneficiaries.

1/6/17	[Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (CAWCS)	Project Planning Meeting. Aberystwyth.
6/17; 7/17; 12/17 1/18	[Redacted] (Cork U) and [Redacted] (Wexford)	Project planning. Phone.
6/17	[Redacted] (Cork U) and [Redacted] (CAWCS)	Project planning. Meeting. Cardiff.
10/11/2017	[Redacted] (Cork U), [Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (CAWCS)	Project planning. Meeting. Aberystwyth. This key meeting brought Irish and Welsh beneficiaries together and marked a significant reshaping of the project. PPP moved away from an emphasis on journeys and routes across the Irish sea and adopted a more 'port' focused agenda.
6/12/2017	[Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (AU). [Redacted] (AU), [Redacted] (CAWCS),	Discussed business plan, detailed costings, contribution of stakeholders. Meeting. Aberystwyth.

Table 2 Engagement with stakeholders

Name	Organisation
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

[Redacted]	[Redacted]

[Redacted]	[Redacted]

[Redacted]	[Redacted]

[Redacted]	[Redacted]

[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

1.9 Evidence of the added value of the Operation to the existing or planned investment in the region. Evidence that the Operation aligns with all relevant regional and thematic strategies.

In Wales

A number of the relevant strategies and policies for PPP were discussed in section 1.3 and these form an important context for the discussion in this section. We focus here, though, on the relevance of the Operation to existing or planned investment in the region.

One of the key mechanisms for investing in the North Wales and South West Wales regions is in relation to the formation of city regions (see the NAW's *City Deals and the Regional Economies of Wales*). As noted earlier, however, concerns have been raised about the possibility that these city regions (based on Swansea in South West Wales and on Liverpool/Manchester in North Wales) will lead to a relative disinvestment in those deprived communities located furthest from the city region core. PPP will help to address that issue by ensuring that there is direct investment to support tourism in these more 'peripheral' areas. Furthermore, PPP will seek to contest any narratives of peripherality by showing how post towns such as Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke are key hubs for an alternative region that encompasses the Irish Sea Basin.

PPP also complements the plans outlined by the Welsh Government to *regenerate communities* in Wales in its *Targeted Regeneration Investment: Guidance for Local Authorities and Delivery Partners* document. In particular, our work with the three port communities has the potential to complement the emphasis that is placed on targeting investment for regeneration in seaside towns.

PPP clearly meshes well with the Tourism, Recreation and Leisure priority outlined in the *Welsh Economic Prioritisation Framework (EPF)*. Tourism here is viewed as a significant opportunity for growth and jobs given the relative importance of the sector in Wales – as well as offering needed opportunities for lower skilled employment. The role of the coast and historic features in the landscape are noted as two aspects of the tourism that Wales has to offer and PPP complements these two emphases well. PPP will have to connect, for instance, with the £12 million that has been invested in supporting the Wales Coastal Path and the £1.5 million that is being invested in the Coastal Communities Fund. It will also be integrated with the Pan Wales Interpretation Plan, coordinated by Cadw, which has the potential to add depth and authenticity to Wales' heritage product, and Cadw's Heritage Tourism project, a £19m project funded by the 2007- 2013 ERDF programme, which has supported developments at key cultural and heritage sites across West Wales and the Valleys. In regional terms, PPP clearly fits in with the emphasis that is placed in the EPF on viewing North Wales' geographic location – specifically in terms of its proximity to Ireland – as an economic asset.

Regional Tourism Networks. PPP integrates well with the priorities of Wales' Regional Tourism Networks – Tourism Partnership North Wales and South West Wales Tourism Partnership – and the relevant county-level Destination Management Plans. For instance, Anglesey's Destination Management Plans notes that one of its action points is to enhance and manage Anglesey's coastal resource. Similarly, two of Pembrokeshire's Destination Management Plans objectives are to re-focus marketing and to create a year round quality experience. PPP dovetails well with this objectives.

Finally, PPP tallies well with the investment plans and economic opportunities outlined in the *The Potential for the Maritime Economy in Wales* document, published by the National Assembly for Wales. The document reports on inquiry, which looked at the economic potential of the maritime economy in Wales, by focusing on the opportunities from marine (also referred to as 'ocean') energy, the role of ports as hubs, key transport links to Ireland, and the strategic approach of the Welsh Government to marine and maritime affairs. The document as a whole emphasises the need to develop stronger and strategic networks between Welsh and Irish ports and yet, the majority of the narrative is based on the economic benefits that may derive from increasing logistical efficiencies and marine capacity more broadly. PPP sees value in developing a different kind of strategic networks between Welsh and Irish ports by emphasising the shared histories that exist between them and the way in which these can be exploited for economic gain.

In Ireland

In Ireland, the Department of Transport, Tourism and Sport have produced a report on People, Place and Policy: Growing Tourism to 2025. The report identifies ports as a priority for the development of tourism and expresses concern (shared by the ferry companies) that the passenger facilities at ports are not currently of a suitable standard. The report notes that 'a number of port companies have ambitious plans to improve their facilities'. PPP aligns with potential plans that would see specific improvements in the ports of Dublin and Rosslare. A renewed infrastructure would be enhanced and complemented by a cultural heritage offering of the kind proposed here.

There has been significant increase in the number of cruise ships and passengers visiting Dublin and that increase is forecast to continue with the widespread growth in cruise business. The operation PPP can help to support and diversify the tourism sector by making the port itself a place of distinct cultural interest.

The tourism strategy for Dublin (Destination Dublin) covers the wider Dublin region, comprising Dublin City Council, Fingal County Council, South Dublin County Council and Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council. The strategy notes that Dublin has become 'stale' in tourism terms and needs more diversified offerings. Though the strategy does not refer to ports or the sea, PPP aligns with this strategy in developing a new operation with links along the south east coast and across the Irish sea.

The most south- easterly county in Ireland, Wexford has a long coastline of 275km. Developments in the cross-maritime area add value to and align with a number of existing strategies and plans. The Local Economic & Community Plan for County Wexford which covers the period up to 2021 states that Wexford aims to be a county that values its natural environment and heritage. The Plan expresses the view that the coastal resources and communities in County Wexford should be supported and their potential maximized; it also stresses the potential for County Wexford's local cultural heritage and natural environment to draw more tourism to the area.

The Plan draws a link between maximizing cultural heritage and developing the arts. The link between cultural heritage and the arts is expressed several times within the Plan: there is clear alignment with PPP and the role of the creative arts in the operation. Further investigation into oral history and efforts to record and preserve memories are also part of the Plan (Sustainable Community Objective 6.1), again aligning with community and creative aspects of PPP. PPP can help to deliver the course and workshops in cultural heritage that are part of the aims expressed within the plan. The Plan names Rosslare in terms of both opportunities and threats. Sustainable Community Objective 6.3 aims to support initiatives that maintain and enhance the marine/coastal

culture and heritage. PPP thus aligns with a statutory document with some weight in terms of actions and achievement of these actions.

While there is strong regional as well as national appreciation for the importance of the significance of Rosslare Europort for the county, there are however a number of challenges facing Wexford. Commissioned by Wexford County Council and completed by the All-Island Research Observatory, NUI, Maynooth, the Wexford Socio-Economic Baseline Report outlines these challenges and opportunities. The South East region's Action Plan for Jobs includes reference to Rosslare and the need to improve visitor experiences at Rosslare Port. PPP aligns with these objectives.

Further, Wexford County Council's Rosslare-Kilrane development plan (<https://www.wexfordcoco.ie/sites/default/files/content/Planning/RosslareHbrAndKilraneLAP12-18/RosslareHarbourAndKilraneLocalAreaPlan2012-18a.pdf>) details plans to develop the Rosslare area for tourism purposes. The development plan details a strategy to maximise the economic potential of the Rosslare port facilities and promote the development of associated port related employment. The development plan itself gives some information on the Ferry industry and history, including the strong connection with Fishguard. This suggests an awareness of as well as an alignment to PPP plans in the cross-maritime area.

1.10 Highlight any potential for displacement of the private sector through the activities to be funded

There will be no displacement of the private sector.

Section 2 –Delivery

2.1 Preferred option for delivery, including the ultimate change sought and final outcomes of the operation

Preferred option

The preferred option for delivery of PPP is **direct delivery by beneficiaries**. There are four joint beneficiaries with University College Cork (HEI), the lead beneficiary working in partnership with Aberystwyth University (HEI) and the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies (HEI) in Wales and Wexford County Council (Local Government) in Ireland. The joint beneficiaries working in PPP have extensive experience and possess complementary skills, experience and facilities with regard to cultural heritage of the maritime area. Because its primary concern is the experience of travel between Ireland and Wales across the Irish Sea, PPP is cross-border in its conception, identity and delivery. PPP is committed to improving the quality of cultural and economic life in port towns via an investigation of the historical experience of travel and sea crossing. A cross-border approach is essential for its delivery via the twinned sites chosen. It could not be achieved by work in only one or two of the sites chosen and would be impossible to deliver without the essential element of cross-border co-operation.

PPP will increase knowledge and raise awareness of the cultural heritage of sea-crossings as well as the history of the ports themselves and build on this increased awareness in order to persuade tourists to build a stay in the port towns into their travel itinerary. The **ultimate change** sought is a greater number of tourists stopping in port towns rather than just passing through, thus engaging with SMEs in the coastal communities and bringing economic benefits to the area. This will increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

The project will deliver the outputs via good community and stakeholder links. By enabling communities to use creative engagement with their historical past to attract visitors and create opportunities, the project will leave a beneficial legacy for the future. PPP findings and displays will have synergies with other tourism and community events, such as annual festivals and events based on historical moments, and help to generate income for coastal communities. National Museums Wales are a stakeholder and their strategy in place for 'wellbeing' based on fuller engagement with cultural heritage projects helps to inform the PPP operation.

Final outcomes are the capacity of coastal communities to derive tourism benefits which will be felt alike in the port towns in Ireland and Wales.

PPP will be delivered over a four year period with 6 months mobilisation and 6 months demobilisation. The three years of delivery are required to ensure delivery of the outputs from the work-packages and output indicators required for cultural heritage priority of the Ireland Wales programme.

Scoping exercise of the activities necessary to deliver changes with identified ‘must have’, ‘prepared to consider’ and ‘might accept’ activities

As detailed in [Strategic Fit above] PPP emerges from discussions between the current partners as to the best ways of developing further understanding of the rich heritage relating to ports and the histories of travel on the Irish sea. The concept for this project has been developed jointly through discussions between UCC, AU and CAWCS. Initially the project had a focus on ‘routes’ across the Irish Sea and was more broadly concerned with the cultural heritage of these journeys. When Wexford County Council joined the discussions, we became aware of a lot of current activity on the theme of ‘routes’ and a number of different heritage trails under development.

The project was refined to avoid overlap and to bring our own expertise and interests more clearly into focus. The narrower and deeper focus on ports emerged from these discussions and PPP took shape. Discussions with the joint beneficiaries were broadened to include meetings and discussions with stakeholders, including community groups and the ferry companies. During discussion it became clear that Dublin Port is considerably more advanced than the other ports in its engagement with and exploitation of its past history. It is hoped that the other ports will benefit from this experience via the operation, but also acknowledged that there are some disparities.

Consideration of Alternative Approaches to Delivery, including ‘Must Have’, ‘Prepared to Consider’ and ‘Might Accept’ Activities

In order to select the most appropriate delivery model, an economic and outcome-related analysis of potential delivery options was undertaken. This resulted in the following approach:

- A list of possible options was generated and discussed by the project team. The criteria for inclusion of options was the extent to which each could deliver on the project’s objectives.
- This resulted in a shortlist of options and each of these was subjected to detailed qualitative and economic assessment.
- As a result a Preferred Option was identified that had the capacity to deliver all the project’s objectives within an acceptable level of risk.
- This option was then subjected to further financial analysis against both the **Preferred** and the **Do Nothing** options.

The process was undertaken in accordance with the *HM Treasury's Green Book of Guidance*, as required for public sector investments. This process included:

- Identifying and evaluating a number of Strategic Options to meet the business needs identified above.
- Selecting the preferred solution from a list of options shortlisted according to agreed criteria based on the specific objectives of the scheme
- Producing economic appraisals for both the Preferred and the Do Nothing options, in accordance with the HM Treasury's Green Book of Guidance. This included assessing the costs and benefits of the proposed project over the useful life of the asset.
- Assessing the economic risks for each of the shortlisted options, including the risk that project outcomes are sensitive to economic influences.

Must Have

To achieve its aims of improving the competitiveness and sustainability of tourism in port towns, PPP must have:

- the capacity to research and reflect upon the cultural heritage of the port towns
- adequate forms of display that can attract tourists and convey the essential information
- scope to include creative responses in the present as a way of communicating the deeper meanings of cultural heritage to coastal communities themselves
- Operation over sufficient time to deliver key outputs
- Cross border partnership to maximise benefits and add value
- Relationship between HEIs, local government and community partners
- The capacity to disseminate information effectively

Prepared to Consider

- Smaller operation for shorter period, though this might not allow the aims of the operation to be realised
- Excluding Dublin Port from the operation based on its unique situation: of the five ports, it is the only one situated in a city; the busiest in terms of existing transport and tourism; and the most developed in terms of existing engagements with its cultural heritage. The absence of Dublin Port would deprive the operation and the resulting tourism network of vital experience and synergies.

Might Accept

- Shorter operation within the programme, though the nature of the network is likely to require time to develop and embed.
- Fewer partners: potential problems of sustainability reduction in a physical presence would minimise impact

Further analysis of a short list of potential delivery options. These options include a ‘do nothing’ option.

In accordance with the HM Treasury’s Green Book of Guidance and Capital Investment Manual the ‘Do Nothing’ option has been considered as a benchmark for potential value for money.

Option 1: The Do Nothing Option

- This would maintain the status quo and continue to see lack of investment in the port towns and the likelihood of further decline.
- This would not support the closer relationship between research into economic generation amongst the partner institutions and the various associated organisations and businesses that would benefit from that closer relationship
- This would not strengthen resilience within those businesses that depend upon tourism, particularly post Brexit and with the economic uncertainties that may follow.
- This would not increase capacity in natural and cultural heritage through cross-border collaboration and the development of networks.
- It would lose the opportunity to create confidence in the potential of the port towns to market themselves as distinctive due to their unique heritage.
- It would not support the Welsh and Irish Governments’ aims, objectives and priorities in the area of increasing tourism and improving the wellbeing of its citizens.

Option 2: Small Scale Operation.

- This option was considered by the partners as a means of reducing the level of commitments in the project in the event that modest achievements could be made for low levels of investments.
- It was considered that most of the contact with community groups, organisations and businesses would be through electronic means with no, or few, face-to-face meetings.
- This option would still contribute towards increased levels of tourism, creating jobs and promoting economic growth.
- The small size of the operation would prevent it from undertaking any major initiatives and its focus would be more limited.
- The reduced costs, smaller scale operation and reduction in a physical presence within the port towns would minimise impact and was likely to

reduce the 'buy-in' from stakeholders and so this would not demonstrate value for money.

Option 3: Medium Scale Operation.

- The primary objective of this proposal is to increase visitor numbers and thereby to create jobs and increase growth. This option would achieve the primary objective.
- It will provide platforms and an interface where communities and businesses across the two regions can connect with researchers and with each other to promote new and innovative approaches to increased tourist stay and spend.
- It will provide the necessary resource to make impact and have legacy.
- It will strengthen resilience, post Brexit, within those businesses that depend upon tourism.
- It will complement other, recent developments and investments such as Visit Wales and will increase capacity in the area of tourism and community development to the benefit of the region and of Wales.
- It contributes to the Welsh Government's aim to build healthier, wealthier and more resilient communities in addition to increasing tourist number.
- The size of the operation would fit well with the 'Bigger, Better, Fewer' approach to the promotion of Wales as a tourist destination as it would enable good working relationships with other relevant stakeholders, allow for impact and legacy.

Option 4: Large Scale Operation.

- Consideration was given to developing a much larger operation that would expand out even more widely from the port towns. This option would achieve the primary objective but would require significantly larger investment.
- There is a danger that this type of approach may be seen as imposing resource onto communities as distinct from developing resources with communities.
- The operation may 'swamp' other complementary initiatives and thereby not build a constructive partnership with other bodies already working in this area.
- The risk of developing a large scale operation is higher and the legacy issues are more difficult to address.
- This option was considered to be high risk and not offer good value for money.

After full consideration it was decided that option 3 – Medium Scale Operation offered the best means of achieving the outcomes and the best value for money.

As part of the consideration of alternative options for delivery PPP undertook a SWOT – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats —analysis for the **Preferred Option**:

<p>Strengths</p> <p>Draws on existing academic and sector expertise</p> <p>Builds on strong existing connections between a number of the beneficiaries</p> <p>Strong governance arrangements based on experienced beneficiaries</p>	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p>Partnership between the four beneficiaries is new</p> <p>The relationship between the ports may be threatened by competition. This might lessen the willingness to collaborate in shared cultural heritage endeavours</p> <p>Disparities between Dublin Port and the other four ports named as part of the project</p>
<p>Opportunities</p> <p>Potential to bring real economic benefit to the coastal communities</p> <p>Opportunities to develop new activities via deepening relationship with stakeholders</p> <p>Integrates community voices and enables coastal communities themselves to shape the direction of the operation.</p> <p>Potential for strong synergies with small tourism businesses in the port communities.</p>	<p>Threats</p> <p>Delivery on the ground may be affected by external changes, in particular the effect that Brexit arrangements will have on the ports themselves.</p> <p>Levels of economic deprivation may threaten community engagement with the project, as benefits may take time to prove</p>

2.2 Delivery model to be utilised.

The PPP operation will be directly delivered by the four beneficiaries. PPP is a collaborative project to be delivered within the following Work Packages:

Details of Work-packages and associated Activities

Work Package 1

WP number	1	Start Month 1		End Month 48		WP leader: UCC
WP title	Project management and Governance					

Objectives

- To ensure transparent and effective governance
- To ensure value for money for the operation.
- To ensure delivery of the project objectives
- To secure compliance with WEFO regulations
- To monitor delivery of project outputs and monitor expenditure and monitor risk register.

Description of work

As lead beneficiary, UCC will manage PPP to ensure delivery of the output indicators. A 6 month mobilisation period will be followed by a public launch event to advertise PPP to all interested stakeholders. Governance will be structured via:

- Programme Board
- Project Management and Monitoring Board consisting of external advisors to PPP
- Stakeholder Advisory Group [Membership of 10; to be sourced as part of next phase]
- Internal reporting managed by the PI working with beneficiaries
- Meetings of Project Management and Monitoring Board to be held quarterly in the first 18 months; followed by meetings every six months thereafter.
- Where possible regular operational meetings will use Skype / FaceTime / WhatsApp in order to keep costs down and to reduce environmental impact.

The Stakeholder Advisory Group will be invited to attend at the six-monthly meetings, and interested parties from coastal community networks will be encouraged to have an active role in meetings following PPP workshops, ensuring transparency and community engagement.

Via WP1, there will be continual internal evaluation of PPP. If needed, external evaluation will be procured through the procurements regulation of UCC and WEFO and will be passed through WEFO before being put out to tender.

WP1 will be responsible for all paperwork associated with the Operation, to ensure all documents are kept in such a way as to facilitate audit and long term storage for audits after the closure of the Operation. Paperwork will include demonstration that the output indicators have been undertaken and achieved.

WP1 will link with WP6 to ensure that governance is transparent and that there is a connection between internal and external communication strategies. Where feasible, WP1 has responsibility for interactions with the other cultural heritage Operations working under the Ireland Wales programme, and also under other EU Operations where these might interact in the maritime area.

Deliverables

1.1 Collaboration agreement

1.2 Minutes of all meetings

1.3 Record of delivery against output indicators.

1.4 Progress reports at six-monthly intervals

1.5 Reports on research

1.6 Financial reports for all institutions at required intervals

1.7 Claims to be submitted in a timely manner and managed on a six-monthly basis

Work Package 2

WP number	2	Start Month	6	End Month	40	WP leader: Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies and Wexford County Council
WP title	Creative connections					

Objectives

- To promote creative connections between twinned port communities, and to create a network of arts organisations, artists and community organisations concerned with facilitating a growth in port heritage tourism.
- To use culture in order to raise awareness of the cultural heritage of the ports in the cross-maritime area
- To make intangible cultural heritage more visible and comprehensible via creative responses to this heritage
- To shape a creative legacy that will encourage visitor interest while providing cultural

sustenance for the coastal communities themselves

Description of work

PPP will facilitate cross-border links between arts organisations, local writers and local artists on both sides of the Irish Sea, forming a network of groups and individuals that will facilitate cross-border exchange and cooperation. PPP will commission six local artists and six local writers to work within the port communities, combining literature and the visual arts to create original works. These written and visual productions will be displayed in the ferry ports of Rosslare, Fishguard, Pembroke Dock, Holyhead and Dublin, most likely in the embarkation lounges. Where the ferry companies allow, some works will also be displayed on the ferries themselves. An accessibly-priced publication will bring together all the artistic outcomes in a single volume, and provide a lasting record of the processes and results.

These works of art will be inspired by historical and cultural content provided by academic researchers (examples might include journeys of saints, eighteenth-century travellers, well-known writers and politicians, militia crossings, famine and political refugees, female travellers and seasonal workers). They will also include a nature-writing, art and photography strand. The artists and writers commissioned by PPP will also work with community memories and experiences of port life and sea crossings, running workshops and other community events.

WP 2 will be organized and delivered via the following activities:

- **Year 1:** The formation of Tourism Networks linking arts organisations, arts groups, writers and artists in coastal communities on both sides of the Irish Sea, including a virtual arts forum for each twinning network.
- A call for artistic involvement according to defined topics, related to the cultural heritage of the ports
- Soliciting expressions of interest and applications from creative artists
- Community Workshops in each of the 5 ports; these will involve the commissioned artists and be used to inform the new art works via the mobilization of community memory
- **Year 2:** Ongoing consultation between community heritage groups and the creative artists, enabled and supported by PPP staff
- **Years 3 and 4:** 5 x community launch events (1 per port) to highlight the significance of creative responses to cultural heritage

Deliverables

2.1 Tourism Networks linking arts organisations, local writers and local artists on both sides of the Irish Sea, including arts forums connecting twinned ports.

2.2. New and original creative works to be displayed in the ports in the cross-maritime area

2.3 Community events and publications focussing on the creative engagements and promoting the links and exchanges to local tourism-related SMES and the wider coastal communities.

Work Package 3

WP number	3	Start Month	Year 3	End Month	40	WP leader: Aberystwyth University
WP title	Documentary films					

Objectives

- To draw on academic and local knowledge about the cultural heritage of the sea crossings between the Irish ports, and the ports themselves, in order to develop documentary films of interest to tourists and communities alike
- To use the Tourism Networks developed in work packages 2 and 5 to showcase voices, sounds and scenes from the coastal communities
- To use moving images to create a new awareness of intangible cultural heritage

Description of work

The operation will commission, provide some content for and advise on five short documentary films exploring the history and stories of the five ports with their associated sea crossings, on both sides of the Irish sea. The film makers will work closely with local communities (school children, dockworkers, ferry workers, elderly residents), to uncover their own stories of life in and around the ports. We envisage that these films will be shown on board Stena and Irish Ferries vessels, in ferry terminals in each port, and will be broadcast via a dedicated 'Ports, Past and Present' You tube channel: offering ferry passengers attractively-presented information about the places they are travelling to and from should increase visits and stop-overs in port towns.

WP 3 will be organized and delivered via the following activities:

- **Year 1:** Develop themes and topics for films: both place-specific and cross-cutting themes. Research historic archive film footage of each port and ferry

route.

- **Year 2:** Commissioning of filmmakers to work on defined topics, related to the particular cultural heritage of each of the ports as well as cross-cutting themes
- Community workshops in each of the 5 ports; these will involve the commissioned filmmakers and be used to inform the films made via the mobilization of community memory
- **Year 3 and 4:** Launch screenings, one in each of the 5 ports
- **On-going** consultation between community heritage groups and the filmmakers, enabled and supported by PPP staff

Deliverables

3.1 5 x 5-10 minute non-fiction films on the history and heritage of the 5 port towns and 3 sea crossings that will help to encourage tourists to visit the port towns.

3.2 Film screenings on ferries, in port terminals and in local communities.

Work Package 4

WP number	4	Start Month	Year 4	End Month	48	WP leader: UCC and Wexford County Council
WP title	Bringing the Past to Life					

Objectives

- To increase tourism visits and tourism spend in port communities, by raising an awareness of the cultural heritage of port towns and creating new heritage related tourism opportunities.
- To make cultural heritage easily and freely accessible and to increase engagement with the past
- To create a new sense of the rich history that lies beneath journeys across the Irish sea
- To use artistic engagements with the past to deepen and enhance community and tourist perceptions of the area of the operation
- To utilise the new Tourism Networks created to increase levels of cooperation and information exchange between tourism authorities, local authorities, heritage organisations, museums, tourism-related SMEs and local groups on both sides of the Irish Sea.

Description of work

This WP has responsibility for visualization of the cultural heritage via graphic displays across the five sites. WP 4 will further provide accessible pathways to new interpretations of the maritime past by developing visualisations (story maps, geo-located maps) of past sea crossings and the history of the ports. These will be available via mobile apps that can be downloaded before, during and after travel and which will give depth and richness to the experience of sea crossings. Apps will also exist as a resource for communities to use and develop. PPP will use Instagram and other social media to invite tourist responses and generate new stories.

WP 4 will be organized and delivered via the following activities:

- **Year 1:** Research that puts the modern history of the 5 ports into the context of the deeper history of landing places and points of embarkation
- **Year 2:** Planning and commissioning and procurement of graphic display boards for location in each of the five ports
- Development of digital visualisations of the story of port life in the past, to be made available via mobile apps
- **Year 3:** Installation of graphic display boards across the five ports
- **On-going:** Continuing public engagement via social media and open access digital technology

Deliverables

4.1 Graphic panels on display in the five ports

4.2 Free mobile apps available to tourists to use and which communities can access and develop.

4.3 A Tourism Network bringing together tourism authorities, local authorities, heritage organisations, museums, tourism-related SMEs and local groups on both sides of the Irish Sea.

Work Package 5

WP number	5	Start Month		End Month		WP leader:
		24		Month 48		CAWCS
WP title	Community events and knowledge exchange					

Objectives

- To facilitate knowledge exchange between the beneficiaries, community organisations, local museums and local communities
- To build capacity in coastal communities

Description of work

The project will organize five day-schools targeting local communities in and around the port towns. Working with local museums and historical societies we aim to improve historical knowledge (tourist literature can be unreliable or inaccurate) and provide high quality reliable historical content that will enable cross-border businesses to enrich the tourist experience. The project will also deliver specific expertise relating to targeted use of social media and best practice in the development of heritage-related tourism. The day schools will target accommodation and service providers and those working in water-based activities (kayaking, boat trips etc.).

WP 4 will be organized and delivered via the following activities:

- **Year 1:** Each port town will host an **Introductory Workshop Session**, where members of the public and specific invited representatives join members of the PPP team to discuss their aims and ideas for the four-year period.
- Workshops will focus on different aspects of the cultural heritage of the ports, beginning with headings designed by PPP and opening out to respond to community concerns and initiatives. Headings will include: revolution; migration; the history of fishing; work and employment, including community relationships with the ferry companies over time; tourism, its impact and potential.
- In **Years 2 and 3** these ideas will be followed up and continually linked to the other events and projects outlined in WP3 and WP4 (creative community engagements, exhibitions, the documentaries)
- **Year 4:** Each port town will host a **Day-School** combining local and invited speakers. Working with local museums and historical societies these events will be designed to improve historical knowledge, and help the tourist industry make the most of their cultural assets to attract visitors and enrich the tourist experience.

Deliverables

5.1 Increased capacity in coastal communities to disseminate good quality tourist material relating to cultural heritage

5.2 Increased capacity in coastal communities in terms of targeted use of social media and best practice in the development of heritage-related tourism.

1.1.1.1 Work Package 6

WP number	6	Start Month		End Month		WP leader:
		1		Month 48		UCC
WP title	Communication and Dissemination					

Objectives

- To communicate PPP events and activities
- To promote PPP operation and its values
- To produce new promotional material

Description of work

WP6 communicates the work and value proposition of the operation PPP. It will include dissemination via a project website and social media (Twitter and Instagram) to ensure a holistic approach to the Irish Sea. WP6 disseminates the project to coastal communities and stakeholders as well as to other funded projects and other prospective partners in the wider scientific/ research community. Most materials that are for dissemination will be in bi- or tri-lingual format including websites and other publicity material aimed at the public, and where feasible ensuring that contractors and delivery partners can communicate in Welsh, Irish or English as required.

WP 6 will be organized and delivered via the following activities:

- **Year 1 and on-going:** Project website to clearly communicate the activities of PPP as well as offer access to meeting minutes and reports. Blogs detailing on-going projects will also be posted and linked to social media.
- **On-going:** Social media presence on Twitter and Instagram, to clearly communicate to a wide audience the activities of the operation
- **On-going:** Engagement with local and national press, starting with liaison with local press in each of the port communities

Deliverables

6.1 Strong and positive public identity for PPP

6.2 Engagement with public, coastal communities and stakeholders via PPP presence on social media channels

6.3 Project website and Tourism Network web-forums that will include news of PPP events and calls, facilitate dialogue and cultural exchange relating to the work packages, and include all project reports and minutes

6.4 Leaflets promoting PPP events and displays

6.5 Provision of translated materials as needed

2.3 Governance

Joint Beneficiaries

University College Cork will be the lead beneficiary with Aberystwyth University, Centre for Advanced Welsh and Wexford County Council as joint beneficiaries.

See letters in the Annex to this document committing to funding on behalf of each of the beneficiaries.

The governance arrangements for delivery are as follows:

Institutional Governance

The functions of **University College Cork** are performed under the direction of the Governing Body. The Academic Council controls the academic affairs of the University. The main executive management group is the University Management Team, which works in support of the President, Professor Patrick O'Shea. The President's Office includes Senior Vice-President Academic and Registrar, Vice-President for Teaching and Learning; Vice-President for Research and Innovation, and Vice-President for External Relations (OVPRI). The project lead, Claire Connolly (Professor Scale 1 in the university), will report to the Vice President for Research and Innovation and to the Research Division of the University's Finance office. Project member Prof Chris Williams serves as Head of the College of Arts, Celtic Studies and Social Sciences. As such he is also a member of the University's senior management team (UMT), bringing a high level of institutional seniority into the operation itself.

The **Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies** is a dedicated research centre of the **University of Wales Trinity Saint David**. It is managed by a Board of Directors which reports to the University Council.

The Project will be managed in accordance with **Aberystwyth University's** agreed procedures for managing large projects as part of which the University Executive has an overview of all operations and considers/approves at an early stage of development. The University's Council has ultimate responsibility for all major projects. It is chaired by the University President. The Finance & Strategy Committee (FSC) is a sub-committee of Council whose remit includes the scrutiny of business plans and recommends approval to Council. It is chaired by the University Treasurer. The Major Capital Projects Advisory Group is a sub-group of Finance & Strategy Committee and is made up of FSC members and senior representatives of the Executive. It is chaired by the University Treasurer.

Wexford County Council is a local authority. The County Manager has responsibility for all projects.

For **University College Cork**, expenditure will be signed off by Mary Cusack, Senior Research Accountant for the university.

For **Aberystwyth University**, expenditure will be signed off by Emyr Reynolds, Head of Research Finance for the university.

For **Wexford County Council**, expenditure will be signed off by a senior member of the Council's finance division

For the **University of Wales Trinity Saint David**, expenditure will be signed off by Mark Rainey, Head of Finance of the University of Wales.

Operation Governance will be structured via:

- A Programme Board
- A UCC Project Management and Monitoring Board
- Stakeholder Advisory Group [Membership of 10; to be sourced as part of next phase and drawn from list presented below, p. 56]
- Internal reporting managed by the UCC Project Manager working with beneficiaries

Programme Board: At operational governance level, there will be a Programme Board which will ensure high-level coordination across the beneficiaries. This will be made up of the four joint beneficiaries. The Programme Board will oversee the whole operation, and approve the required documentation to enable knowledge transfer and research for business to take place. The Programme Board will also be responsible for all contractual obligation and procurement within the Operation. It will include senior representatives from each institution.

Terms of Reference:

The Programme Board will have the following responsibilities –

- Oversight of operation management
- Review reports from the Lead Partner internal Monitoring Group on financial and non-financial progress of the operation against the delivery plan
- Review feedback from the *Stakeholder Advisory Group*
- Ensure appropriate monitoring and evaluation is taking place
- Review the operation risk register
- Recommend action to ensure compliance with Agreement Letter
- Ensure due diligence and make audited reports available upon request

Meetings: The Programme Board will meet twice a year, alternately in Ireland and Wales.

Project Management and Monitoring will be conducted via the **UCC Internal Monitoring Group** will review the progress of the operation.

Membership: Head of College of Arts, Celtic Studies and Social Sciences; PPP Postdoctoral researcher; Prof Claire Connolly; member of the OVPRI (Office of the Vice President for Research and Innovation) and representative from the Finance Office (Research); College Finance Analyst (College of Arts, Celtic Studies and Social Sciences).

Terms of Reference: The Monitoring Group will have the following responsibilities

–

- Monitor progress of lead and partner beneficiary against the approved delivery profile

- Keep expenditure on track

 - Review compliance issues to include State Aid and procurement

 - Review risk register

 - Review progress against targets and make recommendations for remedial action as required

 - Receive reports produced in accordance with the Monitoring and Evaluation plan

 - Ensure adherence to application of the criteria for selecting activities to be funded

 - Review feedback from the Stakeholder Advisory Group

 - Report to the Programme Board

 - Review the draft Progress Report to be submitted to WEFO and approve final version

Meetings: The Monitoring Group will normally meet quarterly, and more frequently if needed.

Beneficiary Project Board

Each beneficiary will operate an internal Management Group that will be responsible for day to day management and governance of the elements of the operation that they are responsible for as beneficiaries

Membership: Senior project staff member, research staff, financial administrator, project administrative staff where appropriate.

Terms of Reference: The internal Management Groups will have the following responsibilities

Direction and management of the delivery team

Management of collaborations with external partners

Management of procurement, other expenditure & internal financial reporting

Management of publicity and events

Delivery of the Monitoring & Evaluation plan

Implementation of recommendations from Steering & Monitoring Group and Project Boards

Report progress to the lead beneficiary and draft a Progress Report

Ensure compliance with Collaboration Agreement

Meetings: The Local Management Groups will meet at least weekly at each site, and more frequently when required.

Stakeholder/Advisory Group

Stakeholders to include select representatives to be drawn from the following list:

Anglesey County Council

British Ports Association

Bro Cybi Ministry Area Council and St Cybi's Regeneration Project

Ceredigion Museum

Crawford Art Gallery, Cork

Dublin County Council

Dublin Port

Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council

Fáilte Ireland

Fishguard and Goodwick Chamber of Trade and Tourism

Heritage Council

Holyhead Maritime Museum

Holyhead Port

Irish Ferries

Irish Heritage Council

National Library of Ireland

National Library of Wales

National Maritime Museum, Dun Laoghaire

National Museums Wales

National Trust Wales

Port of Milford Haven and Pembroke Dock
Rosslare Community Development Association
Rosslare Harbour Maritime Heritage Centre
Rosslare Europort/Irish Rail
The Royal Commission for Ancient and Historical Monuments in Wales
St Davids Diocese Tourism Group
Stena Line
Ynys Cybi Landscape Partnership
Visit Wales
Visit Wexford
The Welsh Arts Council
West Wales Arts Centre

Remit: Stakeholder Advisory Group will review the scope in the operation and provide advice on overall direction and specific issues

Membership: The Operations Manager and representative from the beneficiaries, representatives from selected industrial, central and local government stakeholders.

Terms of Reference: The Stakeholder Advisory Group will have the following responsibilities:

Receive reports on the progress of the operation

Provide advice on priorities

Identify opportunities for increasing the economic impact of the operation

Advise on linkages with other activities taking place in the region with possibility for collaboration

Contribute to the marketing strategy for the operation

Advise on project sustainability possibilities

Meetings: The Stakeholder Advisory Group will meet annually, with a representative also attending the Programme Board.

2.4 Operational Delivery

This will utilise the delivery model described in the Work Packages (2.2)

PPP will be led by the UCC Project Manager and supported by the academic lead and assisted by administrative staff. The Project Manager will oversee the activities of the employed research staff who will be responsible for ensuring

compliance with WEFO guidance and recording activity with respect to the outputs.

2.5 Public funding (including EU funding) in the last 5 year period;

[Redacted]

2.6 Track record of delivering similar operations, including formal evaluations of any previously delivered EU and /or publically financed operations – outlining evaluation recommendations and improvements implemented as a result

UCC and **Aberystwyth University** and the **University of Wales Trinity St David** have received funding for Ireland Wales Co-operation operations in the past. However as these earlier operations did not concern cultural heritage, the evaluation recommendations and improvements are not relevant to this application.

The **Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies** has a 30-year track record of successfully delivering publicly-funded team-based research projects. These are chiefly funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council and no formal recommendations for improvements are made in this context.

Wexford County Council have been delivering on visitor experience for many years, most significantly the initiation of the Irish National Heritage Park, the initiation and delivery of the experiences at the 1798 Centre and the Enniscorthy Castle experience . Wexford Co Council has also worked in cooperation with other groups to deliver and develop major visitor experiences in the county such as Hook Lighthouse experience, JFK Dunbrody Famine ship, Ros Tapestry, Athaneum in Enniscorthy as well as co-ordinating major historical events such as the 1916 celebrations. In addition, the Norman Way has been instigated by Wexford County Council in 2017. The successful delivery of the many projects undertaken is constantly measured by large visitor numbers on an on-going basis and the delivery of such projects are constantly subject to audit from national bodies.

2.7 Any other research evidence supporting the need and approach taken for this proposal

LOCAL AUTHORITY RESEARCH

Wexford Council Council's Tourism Office notes that passenger numbers through Sea Travel have decreased in recent times with an increase in passengers travelling through air travel as the key method of international transport.

However, the docks and ports have a heritage and cultural history that should be recorded, curated and to some level, preserved; in particular, the connection of the Irish and Welsh coasts covered under the project and the heritage of sea travel for thousands of years. This history could be lost forever if not recorded and utilised to connect this generation with past generations.

RESEARCH INTO TRAVEL IN WALES AND BEYOND

Three major research projects at CAWCS funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council provide evidence of the need and approach taken by PPP and also make available archival and cultural sources that will be directly pertinent to the operation. These are: 'Wales and the French Revolution' (2009-12); 'The Cult of Saints in Wales' (2013-17); 'Curious Travellers: Thomas Pennant and the Welsh and Scottish Tour 1760-1815' (2014-18). Outreach events held throughout Wales in relation to these projects have demonstrated clear public interest in connections and movement within the Irish Sea area, and the demand for accessible information about early cult sites such as that of Saint Cybi at Holyhead, about routes and modes of travel, and about historical events which now form part of local legend, such as the French Invasion of Fishguard in 1797.

DEEP MAPS: WEST CORK COASTAL CULTURES

A project led by UCC and funded by the Irish Research Council (2015-2018) has suggested the role of cultural heritage in sustaining positive relationships between humans and our environment. This project focuses on coastal environments and the way in which they are reservoirs of knowledge: personal, cultural and environmental. The project findings show that a more holistic approach to coastal knowledge improves public understandings of the value of the coast.

EU REPORT ON GETTING CULTURAL HERITAGE TO WORK IN EUROPE

Getting Cultural Heritage to Work for Europe was produced by a H2020 Expert Group on Cultural Heritage. It argues that the European Union should vigorously promote the innovative use of cultural heritage for economic growth and jobs, social cohesion and environmental sustainability. According to the report: 'Cultural heritage is a significant force for 21st century Europe. Not only is it at the heart of what it means to be European, it is being discovered by both governments and citizens as a means of improving economic performance, people's lives and living environments'.

THE CULTURAL VALUE OF COASTLINES

The Cultural Value of Coastlines is a two-year UCD interdisciplinary research project funded by an award of €220,000 from the Irish Research Council (2017-2019) to investigate the cultural influences and impacts of ecosystem change on the Irish Sea coasts. The project involves archival and field research in Dublin Bay, the Cumbria coast, and Strangford Lough, as well as knowledge exchange and engagement with coastal communities.

BIBLIOMARA

BiblioMara is a project that was initiated and funded by the Heritage Council of Ireland. The aim of the project was to create as comprehensive as possible annotated indexed bibliography of cultural and maritime heritage studies of the Irish coastal zone. The research team engaged in the work on BiblioMara included: the Coastal & Marine Resources Centre (UCC) (Project Co-ordinators), the Department of Béaloideas (UCC) and Meitheal Mara (Cork). Stage I of the BiblioMara project was undertaken in the period from November 2002 to October 2003 and collected references for the Republic of Ireland. Stage II of the BiblioMara project was undertaken from October 2003 to January 2004 and expanded the bibliography to the island of Ireland to include Northern Ireland. BiblioMara has however not been updated since this point, however, evidencing the need to refresh and renew our shared sense of the cultural heritage of coastlines in the cross-maritime area.

2.8 The required legal basis for delivering the stated activities; the necessary governance arrangements for delivery.

Each of the beneficiaries has strong corporate governance arrangements in place.

UCC is a Higher Education Institution with a remit for teaching and research.

Wexford County Council has a longstanding role in job creation, economic development and tourism development which was further strengthened in the Local Government Reform Act 2014. WCC have therefore the required basis in delivering the stated activities of improving visitor experience and job creation.

The University of Wales Trinity Saint David is a Higher Education Institution with a remit for research.

Aberystwyth University is a Higher Education Institution with a remit for teaching and research.

2.9 Outline assessment of the primary risks and any dependencies that are critical to the successful delivery of the operation

Risks, Assumptions, Issues and Dependencies for Ports, Past and Present

Identified Risk	Effect of Risk on Operation	Control/Mitigation Strategy	Risk and Date	Owner Review
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Failure to identify and implement effective procurement strategy for commissioning of artwork.	Audit failure and potential loss of grant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thorough cost/benefit analysis of procurement options to be undertaken with the support of the Lead partner's Procurement Officer 	<p>Project Manager reporting to Project Board and Senior Responsible Officer.</p> <p>Quarterly</p>
Failure to secure all necessary support from potential stakeholders and targeted areas.	Operation may not have support/ownership in the target towns and outcomes may be limited. Exit strategies may also be compromised.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust engagement plan. • Ensure strong representation by potential stakeholders onto Stakeholder Advisory Group • Regular feedback on stakeholder engagement from partners 	<p>Project Manager Quarterly reporting to Project Board</p> <p>Quarterly review</p>
Failure to demonstrate a sustainable operation	Operation will not achieve its outputs and targets if funding is not carefully controlled.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust revenue costings with sufficient input from key businesses and researchers • Funding sources validated against proposed delivery vehicle • Full market intelligence audit to understand markets and audiences 	<p>Project Administrator reporting to Project Manager including achievements against targets and all to Project Board.</p> <p>Quarterly</p>
Anticipated wider demand for Ports – Past and Present	Operation compromised and may not achieve potential.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners have ongoing relationships with many 	<p>Regular review against plans & targets by Project</p>

<p>does not materialise</p>		<p>organisations in the selected areas that can be utilised and further developed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust action plan for public engagement and dissemination. • Proactive engagement of community groups, relevant organisations and businesses within the port towns including using proven track record of engagement by partners. 	<p>Manager with all partners and to Project Board, making necessary adjustments. Quarterly monitoring.</p>
<p>Lack of clear links between the project and the partner organisations' key strategic priorities leading to a loss of opportunities.</p>	<p>The operation may not develop beyond the initial funded period. The operation may be limited by lack of 'join-up' with other complementary initiatives.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior staff within the partner organisations to continue to have a good understanding of the Ports – Pat and Present project. • Regular reporting and public engagement and dissemination strategies both within and 	<p>Project partners On-going Annual review of strategic monitoring by Project Board and Senior Responsible Officer 6 monthly review</p>

		<p>outside of partner institutions will ensure their continued commitment to the aims of the project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project team will also seek to identify opportunities to highlight the progress and achievements of the operation. 	
Lack of clear senior management ownership and leadership	Operation is not fully supported and becomes marginalised.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular review meetings of Project Board (quarterly) and Advisory Committee (six monthly) and reporting on progress. • News updates through internal and external communication channels 	<p>Project Manager to Project Board</p> <p>On-going review of strategic monitoring by Project Board and Senior Responsible Officer.</p> <p>Opportunities for public engagement and profile raising.</p> <p>6 monthly reporting.</p>
Lack of understanding of EU regulations	Operation does not comply with EU rules and is at risk of failing audits and clawback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expertise gained on regulatory compliance during other Interreg Ireland Wales 	<p>Project Manager</p> <p>Regular discussion with relevant staff in Lead partner organisation</p>

		<p>operations will be used to inform Ports – Past and Present.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any necessary legal or compliance advice will be sought as part of the project mobilisation process and throughout the duration of the operation. 	<p>and among other partners as appropriate.</p> <p>Quarterly reviews.</p>
<p>Difficulties arising following BREXIT</p>	<p>Funding for the operation ends prematurely and reduces outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that operation commences on time to benefit from Treasury underwriting. Monitor all developments carefully to ensure full compliance and closely check underwriting issues keeping project team informed of developments. 	<p>Project Manager and Project Board.</p> <p>Quarterly reviews.</p>
<p>Project over- or under-spends its budget.</p>	<p>Overspend will result in some ineligible expenditure which may cause financial difficulties for partner organisations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial administrator appointed. Quarterly financial profiles of spend against budget and outputs. 	<p>Project Administrator and project Manager reporting to Project Board.</p> <p>Quarterly reporting.</p>

	Underspend will result in some funding being unclaimed and the overall anticipated budget may be at risk.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One financial re-profile anticipated. 	
Project staff leave during operation.	<p>There may not be relevant capacity or expertise within the partner organisation or with other partners.</p> <p>The operation could be weakened and become compromised.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The work packages will be supported by two or more partners to ensure that in the event of an individual leaving other team members could continue to work. • The Project Board will monitor achievements carefully and propose any necessary changes or adjustments to ensure that targets are met. 	Project Manager reporting to Project Board.

More detail may be added to the risk register during the Mobilisation period, post approval, by the Project Manager and reviewed on a quarterly basis in accordance with WEFO reviews. It will be populated as the project progresses.

Section 3 –Financial and Compliance

3.1. Brief Description

PPP will operate over a 48 month period.

3.2 Evidence Requirements for Assessment

Demonstrate how long the organisation/business has been in existence;

University College Cork is a body established by charter in 1845.

Wexford County Council has been in existence for the past 114 years, constituted into existence in 1898.

The University of Wales Trinity Saint David is a body established by Royal Charter in 1828

Aberystwyth University (AU) was established in 1872 and incorporated by Royal Charter in 1889.

Demonstrate when it was constituted or registered as a business or charitable body.

University College Cork was registered in 1908 Legal registration number: CHY2199802/1691 under Statutes/Universities Act (1908/1997)

Wexford County Council was constituted in April 1899 on holding of the first meeting of the Council.

The University of Wales Trinity Saint David is a body established by Royal Charter in 1828.

Aberystwyth University is a registered charity. No 1145141. The Business Registration number is: RC000641. (01/01/1900).

Declare the existence or absence of conflicts of interest e.g. direct or indirect economic interests, political or national affinities, family or emotional ties, or any other relevant connection or shared interest.

There are no conflicts of interest. There are no known conflicts of interest with regards to the PPP Operation. For the purchasing of goods and services where this should arise, both national and European Procurement Policies will be complied with and identified actions implemented.

Provide full details of any previous (or pending) County Court Judgements relating to any individual and/or organisation or business related to this bid. This must also include details of any criminal involvement or dissolved companies.

None.

Provide an initial outline breakdown of costs linked to the planned activities required for mobilisation (i.e. preparation for delivery) and delivery of the operation.

The costs summary below (Table 1) indicates indicative draft costs for the start-up phase (6 months), delivery phase (36 months) and closure phase (6 months). Claims will be prepared and submitted every 6 months. See the Annex to this document for full Budget (for further detail, see Annex 3). Cost Summary of the PPP Operation is as follows:

Table 3

[Redacted]

The intention to implement any Simplified Cost options should be stated and explained. For example, if a flat rate option will be applied, details of the rate and the sector (e.g. higher education) it will be applied to should be provided, as well as identification of the precise elements of the operation that will operate the flat rate option. Simplified costs may also include options around unit costs.

PPP will implement the Simplified Cost options (15% of staff costs).

The applicant (as lead beneficiary) should provide details of its state aid status and that of all potential/planned joint beneficiaries.

There will be no state aid.

Where any component of the operation could potentially be classed as 'net revenue generating' under Art. 61 of the Common Provisions Regulation, initial details of income sources and forecasts should be provided.

There will be no net revenue generated under Art. 61 of the Common Provisions Regulation.

3.3 The Funding Package

Details of the proposed funding package should be provided. If the funding package is restricted by programme or EU Regulations, for example, state aid, this will need to be stated. Details should include:

The level of EU structural fund financial support required and how this amount is the minimum necessary for the operation to proceed;

All co-financing costs are given in Table 3 above. All co-financing will be directly from matched staff time which will be dedicated to the PPP Operation and time-sheeted accordingly.

Joint beneficiary arrangements in respect of co-financing;

Each partner will contribute 20% of the operation costs.

Co-financing in-kind by source / type and its links to operation costs;

There will be no in-kind match funding.

Any other potential sources of funding that have been considered and/or may be required;

No other potential sources of funding will be required.

An explanation of remaining gaps in the funding package and identified ways in which they might be met;

There will be no gaps in the funding package.

Evidence that all potential funding from non-EU sources have been explored;

There is no potential funding from any non-EU source.

Sources and timing for the introduction of co-financing/ co-financing in kind, with an explanation of any conditions or restrictions in its availability.

There will be no restrictions for the availability of match funding.

Further Criterion:

Ports, Past and Present Operation

Business Plan GATEWAY 1 AND GATEWAY 2

An Ireland Wales project responding to Priority Axis – 3 Cultural and Natural Resources and Heritage (with a focus on tourism)

Joint Beneficiaries: Aberystwyth University, University College Cork, University of Wales Trinity Saint David and Wexford County Council

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GATEWAY 2

Executive Summary

Creating a new future for port towns in the Irish sea basin, based on a deeper understanding of their past

PORTS, PAST AND PRESENT: CULTURAL CROSSINGS BETWEEN IRELAND AND WALES

Executive Summary

Working with local communities, Ports, Past and Present will help to make port towns more enriching places to live and work, and more attractive places to visit. It will significantly develop new opportunities for heritage tourism based on enhanced use of cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

The ultimate changes sought and the final outcomes for the project are:

- Coastal communities enjoy an increased awareness of their cultural heritage and develop new opportunities for heritage tourism.
- Port towns become 'stopping places' and 'spending places' rather than just 'through places' for tourists, with an increase in tourism-related employment
- Tourism Networks are formed between twinned Irish and Welsh ports, linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish Sea.

Specific Objective

There has been a movement of people between Ireland and Wales for thousands of years for reasons of trade, leisure, religion, politics, family, and also in times of war. Our countries have experienced shared histories and profound differences. Ports on both sides also share a history of absorbing migrant labour from other cultures and languages. The PPP operation explores the cultures of the port areas of Dublin, Rosslare, Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock and will bring this heritage to public awareness, both within coastal communities and to increase visitor numbers and enhance visitor experiences. In doing so it will increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

The project aims to bring life and colour to the ports, enhancing the experience of modern travellers of all ages and interests, and encouraging people to spend more time and money in these towns. It will do this by working with tourism

stakeholders and local communities to make passing tourists aware of the deep history of these places. Specifically, the project teams will produce information in various formats, working with port authorities, transport carriers, tourism agencies, and local artists and writers to generate new tourism sites/sights/traffic, and commission creative works in the visual arts, literature and film. New audiences will be sought through digital technology including apps and social media. Irish and Welsh language material will be fully integrated throughout the project content.

PPP will help to make port towns, as a result of their rich cultural heritage, enriching places to visit. In doing so it will significantly develop new opportunities for heritage tourism based on enhanced use of cultural heritage as a driver to economic growth.

To achieve these objectives the project team will set up a series of tourism networks linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations, arts organisations, and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish sea – including a tourism web-forum, information sharing networks, and community events.

Implementation, changes sought and impact

The operation concerns 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation in linked cultural heritage tourism activities. Changes sought are to sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets. By raising awareness and fostering a renewed engagement with the past, the operation will increase capacity for community development of these heritage resources. It will also help to encourage tourists passing through port towns to make longer visits and to stop and spend time in these places of transit.

Outputs

- New tourism network, linking 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism.
- A broad range of media aimed to encourage tourists visiting coastal communities and port towns to spend more time and money.
- Creative outputs which engage tourists with the cultural heritage of these coastal communities.
- 2 FTEs in supported enterprises.

Activities to achieve results

- Research into the maritime and coastal history of the port towns
- Commissioning creative engagements with cultural heritage in order to shape lasting cultural legacies; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns

- Commissioning documentary films that showcase stories and voices from the coastal communities; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns
- Graphic displays of cultural heritage to be located in the ports
- Digital visualisations of past sea crossings and the history of the ports
- Community workshops that share and disseminate knowledge of cultural heritage and improve skills relating to social media use in promotion of heritage-related tourism

Evidence of Need

Ports play a vital role in the economy of Ireland and Wales, providing as they do employment while facilitating trade and creating vital lines of connection between and across borders. However, many port towns are sites of economic deprivation, places that visitors pass through rather than stop in. Coastal communities around port towns depend on the movement of people and goods but, as with visitors, tend not to be deeply aware of the histories and stories attached to the ports.

In both Ireland and Wales, Brexit is likely to have an impact on the geographies of mobility through ports. For example, there has been a Welsh government committee report articulating concerns about the impact of Brexit on Welsh ports. This largely relates to questions around a hard border and customs infrastructure but the role of port towns remains under threat:

<http://www.assembly.wales/laid%20documents/cr-ld11158/cr-ld11158-e.pdf>

With the exception of Dublin, the ports in the PPP Operation are sites of economic disadvantage. The 'Welsh Deprivation Index' (2014), shows that areas of two of our three port towns are some of the most deprived in Wales. Wexford has the 3rd highest rate of unemployed people in all local authorities in Ireland. The Wexford Local Economic and Community Plan states the need to further develop Rosslare Europort and articulates the benefit of maximising the presence of this significant port in the county.

While Wexford County Council regard the location of Rosslare Europort within the county as a major strength and a key access route into Ireland from Europe and the UK, there is also recognition that Rosslare itself is an area of economic need. Small Area statistics for the area around Rosslare Harbour based upon Census data for 2011 have been analysed by Pobal to give a Relative Deprivation score of -4.91. This score is based upon the demographic profile, social class composition and labour market situation of Small Areas in 2011. This is consistent with Co.Wexford as a whole (which has a 2011 score of -5.14) placing the area around the harbour as having a Relative Deprivation score that is *below average* for the country as a whole. Pobal noted commuter counties around the Greater Dublin Area (such as Co.Wexford) experienced the greatest decline in Deprivation Scores over the period 2006-2011.

Dublin Port is the largest and busiest Irish port in the Irish port sector. Dublin Port lies at the eastern edge of Dublin city. The percentage of the population over 65 years of age at 12.6% in the environs of Dublin Port is higher than the national average and the Greater Dublin Area. The population of the Dublin Port area is ageing faster than the national average. (*Report on the Socio-Economic Aspects of the Alexandra Basin Redevelopment Project*) and the Port is important as a large stable employer that provides employment and contributes to the social fabric of the area. Economic development plans for Dublin Port have noted the need for cohesive social infrastructure. Better knowledge of shared cultural heritage can contribute to this aim.

Many economic indicators show that there is a considerable objective need to support economic development in *Wales as a whole*. In 2015, workplace Gross Value Added (GVA) for Wales was 71.0 per cent of the average for the total of all UK regions. Wales had the lowest level of GVA per head in the UK regions (Welsh Government 2017a: 15). Similarly, gross disposable household income (GDHI) in 2015 for Wales was £50.6 billion or £16,341 per head of population. This represented 85.5 per cent of the UK figure (Welsh Government 2017a: 15). Some of the Future Generations Indicators portray a situation in which Wales is seen to be lagging in economic terms behind other UK regions. The latest estimate of the employment rate for Wales from the Annual Population Survey (APS) of those aged 16-64 is 71.5 per cent for the year ending June 2017. The UK rate was 74.2 per cent for the year ending June 2017 (Welsh Government 2017a: 18).

Other indicators demonstrate the evident need for more sustainable and inclusive forms of economic development in *Wales' port communities*. The Welsh Deprivation Index (2014) shows that areas of two of our three port towns are some of the most deprived in Wales: two areas of Pembroke are in the top 4% of most deprived areas in Wales, one area of Holyhead is in the top 10% of most deprived areas, and a further three areas of Holyhead are in the top 15% of most deprived areas in Wales. Figures from 2005 show that these patterns are entrenched; there is an ongoing cycle of deprivation that characterises many of Wales' port communities (<http://wimd.wales.gov.uk/?lang=en>). Further evidence of the existence of poverty and deprivation comes from the fact that many of the port areas in Wales have been designated as Communities First Clusters (i.e. communities characterised by extensive poverty). A significant proportion of Holyhead forms part of the Isle of Anglesey Community First Cluster, while three communities (LSOAs) in Pembroke Dock (Central, Llanion 1 and Pennar 1) form part of Pembrokeshire's Communities First Cluster (<http://gov.wales/topics/people-and-communities/communities/communitiesfirst/clusters/?lang=en>).

Our discussions with stakeholders in the port communities have also testified to the existence of considerable concern about their long-term futures, particularly

in Wales once the Communities First programme is terminated in 2018. The project will seek to promote a better touristic experience – and increase tourist spend – within these communities as a way of helping to ensure their long-term economic vitality. PPP will make the port towns more attractive places to live and work by working with key stakeholders and local communities, finding new ways to keep ferry passengers, cruise passengers and other tourists in the port towns themselves.

Headline details on the operation costs and co-financing package including the financial support requested from the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme.

Total costs of PPP Operation	€3,000,000
ERDF Grant @ 80%	€2,400,000
Contribution from partners	€ 600,000

Objectives, Methodology and Outputs

Our Programme Specific Objective: *To sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets in increasing visitor numbers to coastal communities of the programme area.*

The PPP Operation will work with community groups and businesses in the five port towns, creating opportunities for local talent to flourish and enabling spaces for new ideas to be discussed and encouraged. By building interest in and extending knowledge of the local history embedded in landscapes, built heritage and communities, PPP aims to increase communities’ confidence in the value and attraction of these places to both insiders and outsiders. Having a deeper engagement with, and greater ‘ownership’ of, this material will encourage people working in the tourism sector to find creative and dynamic ways to promote their cultural assets, and make their ‘hidden stories’ better known—from the 1797 French Invasion of Fishguard to the construction of ‘space-ships’ used on the set of *Star Wars* at Pembroke Dock. By drawing material from within communities as well as through research we aim to create a sustainable, renewable source for the development of future ideas.

Through work-packages 2 and 3 community members will be working alongside talented individuals from the creative industries (artists, writers and film-makers); through work-package 4 they will help the PPP team ‘bring the past to life’ by developing multiple forms of sharing information. The Operation will thus directly reinvigorate the tourism sector, providing new visitor experiences and encouraging new approaches to marketing by working closely with key tourism stakeholders such as local authorities, local businesses and local communities.

This will help us to achieve our **Programme Result Indicator**: *to increase the number of overseas visitors to the coastal communities of the Programme area.*

The operation will create a series of tourism networks linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations, arts organisations, and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish sea. It will produce:

- A broad range of media aimed to encourage tourists visiting coastal communities and port towns to spend more time and money.
- New creative outputs which engage tourists with the cultural heritage of these coastal communities.

Table of Programme Outputs

Indicator	Measurement unit	Target value
Productive investment: Employment increase in supported enterprises	Full time equivalents	2.0
Number of new tourism networks promoting cultural, natural or heritage assets	Cross-border networks	1
Number of coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism	Communities	5

Operation management, staff and delivery:

The PPP operation will be delivered directly by an interdisciplinary partnership led University College Cork and managed by UCC and the three other joint beneficiaries: Aberystwyth University, University of Wales Trinity Saint David Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies and Wexford County Council. The institutions will use existing senior staff as PIs, and create, across the operation, new posts for a Project Manager, three Project Officers, two Senior Executives and two part-time Finance Officers who will all help to deliver and monitor the outputs. A Stakeholder Advisory Board will also be created.

The Operation will have a 6 month mobilisation period, a delivery phase of 3 years, and a 6 month closure period. Operational management and delivery have been described both in the Core Criteria and in the further criteria. A **full governance structure** showing the composition of operation Boards and the different staff roles can be found in G2 Section 7 (Management and Governance) below.

Lead beneficiary, University College Cork (UCC) will manage the PPP Operation to ensure delivery of the output indicators. Institutionally the PPP Operation will be overseen by UCC Research Committee. **Internal Project Management meetings** will be held quarterly. The group's tasks will include reviewing the risk register, compliance with all legislation, receiving reports associated with the monitoring and evaluation plan and the results of WEFO verification activity. They will report to the Programme Board and review reports to be submitted to WEFO. There will be regular consultations with the Programme Development Officer (PDO: Breda Curran).

The **PPP Programme Board** will ensure high-level coordination across the beneficiaries. The Board will include senior staff representatives from each of the four beneficiaries. It will meet twice per year and its terms of reference will include having oversight of the Operation, reviewing all reports, reviewing the risk register, and ensuring that monitoring and evaluation is taking place.

Joint Beneficiary Project Boards at the individual institutions will meet weekly. They are responsible for monitoring day-to-day management and governance of the work-packages for which they are responsible. They also ensure collaboration with joint beneficiaries and external partners, correct procurement and other legislation, and report progress to the lead beneficiary.

A **Stakeholder/Advisory Group** will meet annually and will also contain a representative from the Programme Board. This group will review the scope of the Operation and provide advice on overall direction, and aid with specific issues such as sustainability and other activities with collaborative potential. They will also help with the dissemination and marketing of the Operation.

A summary of the key barriers & risks

An updated risk register, with proposed mitigations and allocation of responsibilities, is attached as a separate document in Annex 6. This register will be revised, developed and updated continually in line with the operation's stated governance practice.

Risks identified to date include:

Staffing and management issues:

- Failure to demonstrate a sustainable operation
- Lack of clear senior management ownership and leadership
- Lack of clear links between the project and the partner organisations' key strategic priorities.
- Failure to identify and implement effective procurement strategy for commissioning of artwork, creative writing, and film documentaries.
- Over- or under-spend in budget.
- Project staff leave during operation.

Wider issues:

- Lack of understanding of EU regulations
- Current uncertainties surrounding the effects of BREXIT and difficulties arising as a result of border changes.
- Failure to secure all necessary support from potential stakeholders and targeted areas.
- Failure to create wider demand for Ports Past and Present within the targeted communities

These risks have all been considered and discussed by the operation team, who will continue to revise and update the register during the mobilisation phase.

Further Strategic Criterion

5. CROSS CUTTING THEMES

The Strategic Fit Core Criteria (C1) of the PPP Operation has described several aspects relating to Cross Cutting Themes. Further information is given below.

5.1 How will the Operation fulfil its statutory obligations under all legislation relating to the CCTs

The *Ports Past & Present* team recognise the importance of equal opportunities, environmental sustainability and tackling poverty and social exclusion. We have designated a Champion to ensure that cross-cutting theme aims and commitments are delivered during the project in an integrated way. All partners are public bodies and subject to statutory obligations as such.

5.2 How PPP will align with and support equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming

Promoting equal opportunities regardless of individual's race, gender, age, disability, religion or belief and sexual orientation is integral to the working practices of the partner HEI's as we recognise the importance and benefits of a diverse workforce. Partners will aim for a representative balance of gender, disability, ethnicity and age at all levels of staff. All the partner Universities have action plans relating to the 2008 Researcher Concordat which is supported by RCUK and the UK HE funding bodies. This is an agreement between funders and employers of research staff to improve the employment and support for researchers and research careers in UK higher education. It has seven principles, and principle 6 is that "diversity and equality must be promoted in all aspects of the recruitment and career management of researchers".

Full details of the beneficiaries' policies and commitments regarding **equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming** are given in Gateway 1.

The partner Universities all participate in the Athena SWAN programme, which recognises commitment to advancing women's careers in science, technology, engineering, maths and medicine (STEMM) employment in higher education and research and awards charter marks (UCC and Aberystwyth University have bronze award). The scheme will also include race equality charter marks and the partner Universities will seek to implement policies that result in achieving in this additional charter mark. The *Ports Past and Present* Champion for Equal Opportunities and gender mainstreaming will be the SRO.

All partner universities undertake to meet all statutory obligations under relevant legislation by complying with their Equal Opportunities and Diversity Policies.

These are guided by the Equal Pay Act, Sex Discrimination Act, Race Relations Acts, Disability Discrimination Act (1995), Special Educational Needs and Disability Act (2001), Human Rights Act (1998) and the EU Equal Treatment Framework Directive (2000/78). In addition, partners will adhere to the Codes of Practice issued by the Commission for Equality and Human Rights. Partner's policies will be amended as appropriate to meet the demands of future legislation and best practice. We recognise that Ports Past and Present will benefit from integrating equal opportunities into the project by several mechanisms including a) maximising chances of recruiting talented staff to the project, b) minimising staff turnover, c) creating a healthy and positive working environment. The Universities are committed to complying with the 1993 Welsh Language Act and treat the Welsh and English languages on the basis of equality. Information about the project and publicity and marketing materials will be produced bilingually and our project team include several first language Welsh speakers. We recognise that many of the organisations and community groups that we will work with will not necessarily have formal policies in relation to equality and diversity, disability discrimination and human rights and that establishing policies and achieving recognition of these (e.g. via charter marks) is of benefit, particularly to SMEs.

We are happy to discuss the importance of equality and diversity issues with SMEs with whom we work and to encourage them to put policies in place. We will signpost them to organisations such as SBBS, ACAS, Equally Ours and the Equality and Diversity Forum, who can offer support in this area.

Specific actions will include:

The partner universities incorporate DDA considerations into design of any new buildings and services relating to the operation, with a view to providing an environment in which disabled people can travel to, enter and make use of independently or with support where appropriate. Accessibility will be considered when choosing venues for meetings/seminars/workshops/conferences etc.

The partner HEIs in Wales have Welsh language policies with which Ports Past and Present will comply. Additionally, in line with the Welsh Government's Welsh Language Scheme and Iaith Pawb, the National Action Plan for a bilingual Wales, publicity activity relating to the project will be bilingual wherever appropriate and possible.

The team will ensure that job opportunities are made available to all individuals, including those with protected characteristics in line with the UK Equality Act 2010 and the Irish Employment Equality Acts 1998–2015. We will ensure that job opportunities are advertised through local networks to ensure that local people are aware of any opportunities. All opportunities will also be advertised nationally. We will review good practice guidance for accessibility in respect of

publications/websites etc, such as that produced by RNIB Cymru and the BSI web accessibility CoP. We will ensure that conference and seminar venues are accessible and, wherever possible, close to public transport routes. Partners will participate in Equality Impact Assessments carried out by the partner beneficiaries where appropriate.

Promoting equal opportunities regardless of individual's race, gender, age, disability, religion or belief and sexual orientation is integral to the working practices of the partner HEI's as we recognise the importance and benefits of a diverse workforce. Partners will aim for a representative balance of gender, disability, ethnicity and age at all levels of staff. All the partner Universities have action plans relating to the 2008 Researcher Concordat which is supported by RCUK and the UK HE funding bodies. This is an agreement between funders and employers of research staff to improve the employment and support for researchers and research careers in UK higher education. It has seven principles, and principle 6 is that "diversity and equality must be promoted in all aspects of the recruitment and career management of researchers".

5.3 How PPP will align with and support Sustainable Development

The Sustainable Development Champion for the Ports Past and Present project will be the Project Manager. The approach to Ports Past and Present will take full account of moving to a low carbon economy and is committed to sustainable development. Consequently, the project partners are all well versed in sustainability and the project can contribute to the Welsh Government's commitments in this area via two mechanisms, in order of their tangible environmental benefits:

Mechanism 1: incorporating practical environmental measures within the work done wherever possible (e.g. use of Skype and other means to reduce the number of face-to-face meetings).

- Transport and Travel – promoting green transport initiatives .
- Energy Management – reducing contribution to global climate change by making significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. Welsh HEIs report annually to HEFCW on progress against scope 1 and 2 carbon targets.
- Releases to Atmosphere and Water.
- Waste Management – reduction, reuse and the promotion of recycling.
- Education for Sustainable Development and Global Citizenship (ESDGC) – embedding sustainable development and awareness of environmental issues in curricula across the Universities.

Mechanism 2: influencing the ‘in house’ environmental performance of organisations and SMEs that we work with by encouraging them to embed low carbon technologies and products as part of their core business.

The central purpose of *Ports Past and Present* is to stimulate economic growth via innovations relating to tourism but with due regard to environmental sustainability. The partner universities have broadly similar environmental policies and strategies, including provisions relating to:

Local Environment and Land Use (Ecology and Biodiversity).

Opportunities relating to **mechanism 1** will be identified and acted on. E.g.

- Through the development of a **PPP Eco code** the operation will **promote environmental awareness and good practice in the implementation of activity**. The Eco code will encompass the following activities **Transport** (e.g. reduce need for travel where possible through ICT, co-ordinate and share transport to ensure maximum benefit and environmental sustainability), **Prevention, Reduce, Reuse and Recycle, Biodiversity** (e.g. appropriate site assessments of locations for art works where relevant and liaison to ensure biodiversity and wildlife is not effected during project delivery), **Purchasing, Raising Awareness** (e.g. informing stakeholders and the general public how we are looking after the environment during and through PPP’s work).
- The PPP operation will **Integrate sustainable development into operations undertaking awareness raising and education programmes**. Initiatives to train citizens in heritage and promote environmental protection through PPP will leave a legacy of **increased awareness and transferable skills among coastal communities**.
- PPP will ensure that the dissemination of research and project content will be aimed at the full range of social and economic groups. All partners have good experience in community engagement.
- By promoting the coastal and marine cultural heritage assets, the PPP operation will be aligned to the aims of **Enhancing the environment – particularly the coastal and marine environment to support blue and green growth**.

Lead beneficiary **University College Cork** supports Sustainable Development. In 2007 the University become the first in the world to be awarded a Green Flag from the Foundation of Environmental Education. UCC renewed its Green Flag in 2013 and 2016, and in July 2016 published its Sustainability Strategy committing to be a ‘world-class University leading the drive towards sustainability in Higher Education Institutes and beyond, to our community, region and planet.’ UCC’s Green Campus includes a university-wide module on sustainability, and is student-led, research-informed and practice-focused, demonstrating a strong commitment across all levels and divisions in the University. The university is finding ways to reduce the negative impacts of its purchasing decisions by

implementing green or sustainable procurement policies and processes. These will be fully integrated into the PPP operation. **Aberystwyth University's** procurement policy will also support sustainable development;

Sustainable Procurement – working with suppliers who themselves have sound ethical, environmental and sustainability policies. Aberystwyth University's Corporate Procurement Policy includes:

The University will develop and implement a Sustainable Purchasing Strategy and will use the 'Value Wales Sustainable Procurement Tool' (SPAF) to assess and measure its current position and produce an action plan to further improve its performance. **Aberystwyth University** has been awarded EcoCampus Gold Award following an independent audit of its environmental management system. The award recognises the University's commitment to improving its environment and sustainability, and paves the way for securing the EcoCampus Platinum Award and the internationally accredited ISO14001 environment standard. Aberystwyth University has also been awarded a Green Flag for its Penglais Campus over three successive years (2014-2017) and for Llanbadarn Campus in 2017.

Tackling poverty and social exclusion

The Tackling Poverty and Social Exclusion Champion for the *Ports Past and Present* project will be the Project Manager. The primary objective of the project is to stimulate and create innovative products and processes to improve the tourist offering. This will include an awareness of various issues relating to sustainability. In the medium term, an increase in tourism will result in inward investment, jobs and growth, and so in a general sense, contribute to tackling poverty and social exclusion. Balancing the need to tackle the impacts of poverty now with the need to tackle the issues which will cause people to be in poverty in the future is recognized in the **Welsh Government's Tackling Poverty Action Plan and the Well-Being of Future Generations Act**.

Where opportunities arise to collaborate with operations relating to the **ESF Priority Axis on Tackling Poverty through Employment** we will do so. In the longer term, we see opportunities for the project to leave a legacy in the stimulation of new jobs in the local economies of the identified port towns.

CCT indicators

The measures that we will take to ensure alignment with and support of the CCTs are:

- An Eco Code for the operation will be developed during the mobilisation phase

- Gender ratio for project staff will be monitored during recruitment and, where possible under public sector rules, positive discrimination will be practised
- Balanced representation of gender in all PPP heritage material, including a focus on the role of women in the maritime past
- Disabled access will be assured at all PPP public events

6. SUITABILITY OF INVESTMENT

PPP outputs will be delivered from the Activities and Work Packages described in the core criteria.

6.1 Define the target participants and/or sectors

As described in Gateway 1, the need for the operation is based on the vital role played by ports in the economy of Ireland and Wales. They are places of employment that also facilitate trade and create vital lines of connection between and across borders. Many port towns are, however, sites of economic deprivation, places that visitors pass through rather than stop in. Coastal communities around port towns depend on the movement of people and goods but, as with visitors, tend not to be deeply aware of the histories and stories attached to the ports.

The PPP programme will target a number of participants and sectors in its attempts to boost heritage tourism in the port communities in Ireland and Wales. The target participants include key stakeholders in the public and private sector, including tourism-related businesses, local authorities, and local communities, all of whom would benefit from an increase in tourism in the port communities and a resulting increase in tourism-related employment in these areas in the five currently functioning ferry ports in the cross-maritime area. There will be a positive impact on the well-being of those who live, work and visit the ports involved in the operation. The ports are organized in a twinning pattern based on the current ferry passenger routes and these will provide the foundation for the new tourism network planned:

- Rosslare and Fishguard
- Rosslare and Pembroke Dock
- Dublin and Holyhead

PPP will undertake a range of work packages designed to boost heritage tourism and related employment in the port towns, articulating port history and heritage to tourists in a range of different ways. This will include informing tour operators and potential tourists of tourism opportunities in the port towns through a distinctive marketing strategy, empowering local communities to become involved in the history of their port communities, and establishing tourism networks through which local stakeholders can share knowledge, good practice and take advantage of heritage tourism opportunities.

6.2 Define the barriers facing the identified participants and/or sectors

There are a range of barriers facing potential participants, some of which are common to all potential participants, and some of which vary by participant/sector type. Few potential participants have access to specialist knowledge about the history and heritage of their port towns, with the exception of museum/archive professionals and a few local historians based in the regions. This presents huge barriers to stakeholders who may wish to mobilise this history and heritage to boost tourism in the towns, especially where historical information remains in the archival record (often at a distance from the towns themselves – e.g. in national archives) and has not been widely interpreted in local museums or key local sites. This includes port authorities and ferry companies who may know little about port heritage or the history of journeys through the ports. It will also include locals living in the towns, tour operators and potential tourists. These barriers do not simply relate to access to information, but also access to financial resources to mobilise this knowledge, interpret the heritage, and present this to tourists. Where knowledge of port histories is possessed it rarely includes knowledge about the places linked to the port or journeys through the ports, which will form a key focus of this programme.

Another key barrier relates to the challenges faced by tourism agencies, local businesses and local authorities in targeting tourists who may be passing through ports and who may wish to extend their stay in the port regions. This includes the challenges of identifying and communicating with these individuals, as well as the subsequent challenge of persuading such individuals to spend extra hours or a day in the port area. PPP has a clear strategy for overcoming this challenge.

The ports in the PPP Operation include key areas of economic and social disadvantage in Ireland and Wales, with the exception of large areas of Dublin. Many individuals in these communities will have little engagement with their local port histories as well as benefitting very little from travel through their ports. PPP discussions with stakeholders in the ports have also identified considerable concerns about the long-term economic and social futures of the ports, as a result of the uncertainties surrounding the economy, Brexit, etc. PPP will involve extensive community engagement activities designed to involve local residents, local artists and others in narrating the history and heritage of the port towns.

Explain how the operation will overcome these barriers and ultimately benefit the identified participants and/or sectors

PPP will be led by teams of internationally recognized academics who will interpret the history and heritage of the five port towns for tourists, heritage professionals and local communities, advancing targeted strategies for interpreting this heritage in ways that will boost tourism in each area. In fostering a keen interest in this history and heritage amongst local individuals, groups and organisations we hope to foster a long-term interest in port heritage which will be self-sustaining. We will work with key stakeholders who operate ferry routes and

market cruise opportunities in Wales to develop new itineraries which appeal to potential tourists, and we will work with the ferry companies to develop new ways to persuade ferry passengers to spend great time in the port regions. By taking a holistic cross border approach, PPP will enable stakeholders to share knowledge, experiences and strategies across borders and with different communities. The PPP programme will establish tourism networks which link local businesses with one another and enrol them in our activities, enabling them to learn from the experiences of other stakeholders on both sides of the Irish Sea. The programme team will work to involve individuals from deprived port communities with the programme, working with community organisations, arts organisations and local artists in developing art works and advancing inclusive port histories and narratives. The PPP programme will include a wide variety of community-based activities throughout the timescale of the project, including workshops, film screenings and launches.

6.3 Demonstrate that these activities are not already being undertaken by existing or planned public or third sector support.

No such activities are already being undertaken. There is a demonstrable need for more information and knowledge. In addition, PPP has consulted with other planned INTERREG Operations in the area and there is no overlap of aims or activities. The relationship between PPP and the Holyhead Tourism Attractor Destination project is discussed in Annex 2.

6.3 Demonstrate that these activities are not already being undertaken by existing or planned public or third sector support.

No such activities are already being undertaken. There is a demonstrable need for more information and knowledge. In addition, PPP has consulted with other planned INTERREG Operations in the area and there is no overlap of aims or activities.

6.4 Please outline in detail the potential of the proposed operation to duplicate activity currently being undertaken by the private sector.

The PPP does not duplicate any private sector activity.

6.5 Where the potential for duplication with private sector activity exists, please analyse in detail the potential of the proposed operation to displace the private sector. If displacement is deemed unlikely, please describe the reasons for this.

The PPP does not duplicate any private sector activity.

7. MANAGEMENT OF OPERATION

PPP has the capacity and resources necessary to successfully deliver the planned results, output indicators and activities.

A description of the governance & human resource requirements for the operation showing that you have a clear and detailed understanding of:

7.1 The governance arrangements necessary for delivery of the operation, including the identity and role of the Senior Responsible Officer (SRO);

The **Senior Responsible Officer** for Ports, Past and Present is the Director of the Operation (Professor Claire Connolly) who will report to University College Cork on the progress of the project. She is answerable to the Vice President for Research and Innovation and to the Research Division of the University's Finance office. For full details of Governance structures at University College Cork and at the three other beneficiary institutions see PPP Gateway 1 (Section 2.3)

Lead beneficiary UCC will manage PPP to ensure delivery of the output indicators.

In relation to **JB Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies**, this body is now part of **University of Wales Trinity St David** and aspects of Gateway 1 have been updated accordingly. The University of Wales established the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies as a dedicated research centre in 1985. The University of Wales and the University of Wales Trinity Saint David committed in 2011 to irrevocable constitutional change. Since September 2017 the respective governing bodies of both entities have operated joint governance and administration arrangements subject to the terms of their respective Royal Charters and law. UWTSB will therefore be the legal entity (as joint-beneficiary) for receipt of the ERDF grant and delivery of the operation.

Governance arrangements necessary to deliver the operation will be structured via:

- **Programme Board**

This Board, made up of senior representatives from the four joint beneficiaries will ensure high-level coordination across the teams. It will oversee the whole operation, and approve the required documentation. The Programme Board will also be responsible for all contractual obligation and procurement within the operation. The Programme Board will meet twice a year, alternately in Ireland and Wales, and have the following responsibilities –

- Oversight of operation management
- Review reports from the Lead Partner Monitoring Group on progress of the operation against the delivery plan
- Review feedback from the *Stakeholder Advisory Group*
- Ensure appropriate monitoring and evaluation is taking place
- Review the operation risk register
- Recommend action to ensure compliance with Agreement Letter
- Ensure due diligence and make audited reports available upon request
- Commission external evaluation and review/ act upon recommendations as necessary.

- **Project Management and Monitoring Board (UCC)**

This Board will meet quarterly in the first 18 months and thereafter every six months (more frequently if required) and will be conducted via the **UCC Internal Monitoring Group**. *Membership*: Head of College of Arts, Celtic Studies and Social Sciences; PPP Postdoctoral researcher; Prof Claire Connolly; member of the OVPRI (Office of the Vice President for Research and Innovation) and representative from the Finance Office (Research); College Finance Analyst. The Monitoring Group will have the following responsibilities –

- Monitor progress of lead and partner beneficiary against the approved delivery profile
- Keep expenditure on track
- Review compliance issues to include State Aid and procurement
- Review risk register
- Review progress against targets and make recommendations for remedial action as required
- Receive reports produced in accordance with the Monitoring and Evaluation plan
- Ensure adherence to application of the criteria for selecting activities to be funded
- Review feedback from the Stakeholder Advisory Group
- Report to the Programme Board
- Review the draft Progress Report to be submitted to WEFO and approve final version

- **Partner Beneficiary Project Boards**

Each beneficiary will operate an internal Management Group responsible for management and governance of the elements of the operation for which they are responsible. *Membership*: Senior project staff member, research staff, financial administrator, project administrative staff where appropriate. The internal Management Groups will meet at least weekly on each site and have the following responsibilities:

- Direction and management of the delivery team
- Management of collaborations with external partners
- Management of procurement, other expenditure & internal financial reporting
- Management of publicity and events
- Delivery of the Monitoring & Evaluation plan
- Implementation of recommendations from Steering & Monitoring Group and Project Boards
- Report progress to the lead beneficiary and draft a Progress Report
- Ensure compliance with Collaboration Agreement
- Contribute to the monitoring of actions in support of Cross-Cutting Themes

• **Stakeholder/Advisory Group**

This group will include select representatives to be drawn from the list of interested stakeholders and will have a membership of 10. It will meet annually to review the scope in the operation and provide advice on overall direction and specific issues

Membership: The Project Manager and representatives from the beneficiaries, representatives from selected industrial, central and local government stakeholders. The group will:

- Receive reports on the progress of the operation
- Provide advice on priorities
- Identify opportunities for increasing the economic impact of the operation
- Advise on linkages with other activities taking place in the region with possibility for collaboration
- Contribute to the marketing strategy for the operation
- Advise on project sustainability possibilities

A stakeholder representative will also attend the Programme Board.

7.2 Key management and staff functions considered necessary

PPP will have a team comprising existing experienced staff who will work alongside new staff recruited specifically to complete the operation activities. The various staff roles are summarised below: fuller **job descriptions** are given in Annex 5

Table 7.2: Staff Roles for Ports Past and Present

Staff Role	Responsibilities
Director of the operation (Senior Responsible Officer)	Overall direction and oversight of the operation to ensure delivery as agreed in the Business Plan and Delivery Profile. Reporting on progress and liaising with the JS and the Programme Board.
Academic Staff (existing): PIs	Existing staff in the collaborating institutions will act as PIs, directing and producing research for heritage interpretation, leading specific work package delivery and/or carrying out activities under relevant work packages ensuring that the specific objectives for the work packages and the outputs and results are achieved and disseminated.

Project Manager (Cork). To be recruited.	Working alongside the staff leading/involved in relevant work packages to ensure that the specific objectives for the work packages and the outputs and results are achieved and disseminated. Ensuring compliance with all EU regulations. Specifically tasked with co-ordinating with stakeholders and with the three other Research Officers in the beneficiary institutions.
Project Research and Community Liaison Officers (Wexford, CAWCS, Aber). To be recruited.	Working with PIs to bring findings of academic research into public domain: developing heritage interpretation and dissemination; ensuring compliance. Liaising with community stakeholders; arranging workshops; managing the artistic and writers residencies and/or the film projects; organizing dissemination events and ensuring bilingual/trilingual communication as required.
Senior Executive Assistant. To be recruited.	Working alongside the Director and other staff to ensure smooth running of the financial and logistical aspects of the Operation. Compiling and submitting claims to the relevant authorities on-line, monitoring expenditure and working to ensure the project follows agreed profiles. Liaising with senior staff internally and externally.
Financial Support Staff. To be recruited.	Dealing with financial transactions, procurements, claims, travel and logistics. Taking care of the day to day financial transactions, ensuring that records are kept to a standard suitable for claim and audit purposes and providing advice and guidance to staff on financial and logistical matters. Liaising with the individual institutional beneficiary Finance Departments.

7.3 The skills and knowledge needed for each identified staff member and how these competence requirements will be met through recruitment and / or procurement within the required timeframe;

Job Descriptions for staff, included in Annex 5, identify the skills and knowledge required by each staff member, both existing posts and the new jobs created by the operation. Recruitment will be carried out in accordance with the Recruitment and Selection Procedures approved by each of the beneficiaries. For the Recruitment and Selection Policy for the four beneficiaries see the following links:

- <https://www.ucc.ie/en/hr/recruitment/>
- <https://www.aber.ac.uk/en/hr/jobs-recruitment/>
- <https://www.uwtsd.ac.uk/jobs/>
- <https://www.wexfordcoco.ie/council-and-democracy/job-vacancies>

New staff will be recruited during the mobilisation phase to ensure that the operation is able to deliver within the agreed timescale as shown in GANTT chart in Annex 4. The Principal Investigator of each institution will be responsible for their own staff. Recruitment will be undertaken in accordance with the equal opportunities and diversity measures set out in the Cross Cutting Themes, and will ensure that the operation attracts, selects, and retains the most suitable candidates using appropriate, fair, open and effective methods.

7.4 Confirmation that all resources required for effective delivery is or will be available;

We can confirm that a thorough assessment of the staff and other resource requirements has been carried out by the lead and all of the joint beneficiaries. For practical issues such as office space and equipment please see Section 7.11 below. Assurances of match-funding from the beneficiary institutions were received at Gateway 1 stage (and can be viewed in the Financial table appended at p.71 of the G1 Business Plan). All the required resources are therefore available to allow the effective delivery of the operation, and will be continually reviewed during internal evaluations.

7.5 How staff will be managed and performance indicators identified and monitored

Staff will be made aware from the outset of the project's governance structure. Each institution is responsible for individual line-management (see the diagram of staffing structure above at 7.1). Staff will take part in a Performance Development Review (PDR) process, which brings staff and line managers together to review roles, expectations and development, and sets key objectives for each period. This ensures that all staff have a clear understanding of what is expected from each role, and provides an opportunity to discuss their contribution to the project as a whole. In addition to this more formal structure, management and staff will be engaged in continual dialogue and feedback. Poor performance or other matters of concern will be addressed promptly in accordance with the regulations of each beneficiary institution, and not left to the next review meeting. Progress reports will be relayed regularly to senior staff at the lead beneficiary institution.

7.6 Confirmation that detailed continuity processes are in place to ensure that a strong link between the business plan and the delivery team is maintained and any loss of staff members will not lead to a 'drift' in the agreed delivery

The joint beneficiaries on PPP will sign the Funding Agreement and a Partnership Agreement confirming the conditions of the funding award. An inception meeting will take place between the SRO, the JS and all beneficiary partners (some attending by Skype), and an initial start-up meeting will be held

internally in UCC to confirm the governance arrangements and the monitoring requirements. The information will be transmitted to the joint beneficiaries as soon as possible after this first meeting. Written reports of any meetings held or correspondence relating to the delivery of the operation between the lead partner and the relevant managing authority will be provided to joint beneficiaries in a timely fashion to ensure that all are aware of the outcome of the communication.

All staff will be made familiar with the business plan and its objectives. Links between the business plan and the deliverable activities will be regularly reviewed on a quarterly basis during Programme Management and Monitoring Board (PMMB) meetings. Reports from these meetings will be circulated at all levels, and any concerns will be flagged up to the UCC Research Division by the Senior Responsible Officer at the lead institution. UCC will make full use of the skills and advice of its Quality Promotion Unit in the running of PPP.

In the event that staff leave the operation, all joint beneficiaries will be responsible for ensuring that any replacement staff are familiar with the content of the Business Plan and Delivery Profile and that they understand their role in achieving the objectives of the operation. All records will be kept up to date and other staff members will be familiar with each other's work packages to minimise the risk in the event of staff leaving. New staff will receive proper induction to the operation within their home institution, and will be fully briefed on previous progress in the role they are undertaking.

7.7 A draft exit strategy for staff

The PPP Operation will encourage the professional development of all staff, and the Performance Development Review will help to identify relevant training and development needs. All employing institutions will encourage career progression and promotion, and (where possible and within given resources) endeavour to promote security of employment for staff through re-training and internal redeployment. Note that a small amount has been set aside by each beneficiary institution for potential redundancy payments for staff who have been on the pay-roll for more than two years. Any research data produced by staff who subsequently leave remains the Intellectual Property of the relevant beneficiary institution in accordance with their regulations and funding guidelines.

7.8 All time-critical governance and human resource activities described above must be incorporated into the delivery profile, with a specific focus on those activities that are essential for the preparation for delivery (which will constitute key milestones during the mobilisation of the operation).

The Delivery Profile is included in Annex 3. All time critical governance and HR activities have been included in the delivery profile, including those necessary for mobilisation.

PPP's six-month mobilisation phase will follow the signing of contracts and will commence with an initial WEFO meeting followed by a joint beneficiaries meeting, after which the processes for the employment of new staff will be set in motion. This will be followed by the development of a partnership agreement.

7.9 Provide details of any necessary tender specifications for elements of the operation that will be procured. Draft early tender notifications, Pre Qualification Questionnaires (PQs) or Invitation to Tender (ITTs) and associated draft contracts should be included in an annex to your Business Plan wherever possible.

Any required tender notifications for procurement will be included in the key milestones during the six-month mobilisation phase. The responsibility for compliance in each case will rest with the beneficiary institution leading the Work-package involved and will be in compliance with local, national and European procurement regulations.

7.10 Provide details on initial and ongoing risk identification, mitigation and management. Have regular reviews been timetabled? What thought has been given to contingency planning if identified as necessary, such as in the event of any changes in demand that may impact on the successful delivery of the proposal? Include the identification of any procurement risks, such as securing suitable sub contractors.

Risk identification and risk mitigation will be at the heart of PPP's governance and delivery; they will be a standing agenda item for the Programme Management and Monitoring Board meetings (PMMB). A risk register has been developed and will be maintained, and will be reviewed at all quarterly meetings of the PMMB, and at the six-monthly meetings of the Programme Board. Work package leaders will be asked to develop their own risk register and will report on the risk status to the lead beneficiary on a quarterly basis. Management Group meetings at each partner beneficiary will review, update and amend the risk register as appropriate.

A preliminary register noting potential risks identified in discussions with the beneficiaries and stakeholders was included in Gateway 1 (Section 2.9). This will be updated in the mobilisation phase of the operation to include specific procurement risks and any risks arising from the uncertainty over the effects of Brexit.

7.11 Outline the Management and IT systems, processes, facilities (accommodation & equipment) that you intend to deploy. It is important also to be clear about location and communication requirements.

UCC and the separate joint beneficiaries operate Data Management Policies which define the responsibilities at individual and institutional level of all those involved in data collection, storage and maintenance. Research data will be managed to the highest standards throughout the research data lifecycle: PIs will be responsible for developing and maintaining research data management plans which will follow best practice. All beneficiaries are committed to the notion of the free and open exchange of knowledge alongside best FAIR data practises and the operation's approach to Data Management and Access will reflect this at all times.

In terms of finance data, Finance Officers and Senior Executive Officers will ensure that electronic copies (PDFs) of invoices are kept with supporting bank statements. Backups of documents at the lead beneficiary will be saved on the UCC main network drive on a daily basis, ensuring that data is secure.

The following are the Financial and HR systems used by partners and which will be underpinning financial controls and operations on this project: **UCC**: Agresso and Core HR, **Wexford County Council**: Integra and Core HR, **CAWCS**: bluQube and HERA system, **Aberystwyth**: Agresso Finance and HR. All beneficiaries are fully compliant with the recent 2018 General Data Protection Regulation.

In terms of facilities staff will have access to office space, word-processing equipment and communications at all home institutions: new staff will be thoroughly integrated into the community of the wider institution. Joint beneficiaries will record staff time using their designated internal systems. The team as a whole will use the Microsoft Office package for word processing, email and spreadsheets, and will continue to make use of video conferencing, teleconferencing, Skype and Facetime on a regular basis to assist with communication across multiple locations. The experience of collaborating on the preparation of the Interreg application has provided ample opportunity to test our ability to communicate between the Irish and Welsh institutions.

7.12 Draft closure plans should be provided which include a realistic timescale to begin preparations for the closure of the operation.

The Programme Management and Monitoring Group (whose activities will be archived and available to view) will ensure that all project documentation is gathered and reviewed by the project manager as work progresses. The operation will ensure that staff are in place to carry out any post-closure activity and monitoring activity. The Project Manager will be the key staff member responsible for project closure activity and will ensure compliance with the conditions of grant set out in the Funding Agreement (and any subsequent Variation of Grant letters which amend the offer of grant) throughout the life of the project.

All our delivery activity will be completed before the operational end date (to be agreed with the JS). We will have verified that all the expenditure and activity is in accordance with published guidance.

Project documentation will be archived to facilitate future audit visits: within six months of the closure of the operation a senior officer will double-check that all pertinent evidence has been retained. The project archive will include the location of key records and documents relating to project activity across all relevant media and locations. Evidence of compliance with EU publicity requirements will be retained (see Section 7.14.5 below) to confirm the publicity measures undertaken within the operation. Project closure will proceed as follows (see Draft Closure Plan in Annex 7):

Delivery phase:

- arrangements for reporting accountants to visit/inspect the operation will be made in order to comply with WEFO's requirements
- beneficiaries, operation staff and steering committee members will be briefed on the timescales for closure of the operation
- an operation archive will be created, containing all records and documents relating to the operation's activities
- an inventory of assets with a value greater than £5000 will be created

Before the end of the delivery phase:

- Senior staff members will check that
 - all pertinent evidence and actions have been identified, put in place or are being carried out in accordance with the conditions set out in the Offer of Grant Letter
 - all of the operation's expenditure and activity is eligible for support and investigate any anomalies
- all delivery activity will cease
- all data for the final claim will be collected
- all staff contracts will end, with the exception of the Senior Responsible Officer, Project Manager and Senior Executive Officer (Cork) and finance staff, all of whom will continue to be employed during the closure phase.

During the Closure phase

- Data, synopses and other outputs will be deposited in appropriate repositories (see 6.1.1)
- A final review of the operation's management records will be undertaken
- A final audit/accountant's report will be submitted
- A final evaluation of the operation will be undertaken and a final evaluation report submitted
- A final claim will be submitted

- A final claim report will be submitted
- A final project report will be submitted
- A project Closure Report will be produced.

Post- closure

- The senior responsible officer will answer any queries from WEFO.

All joint beneficiaries will be aware of the process outlined above and will mirror activity in their own organisations. A checklist will ensure that all the required documentation is retained and that sufficient evidence is available to confirm operation activity. The location of all material will be included on the checklist.

A named senior member of staff will be nominated by each of the joint beneficiaries to maintain ownership and responsibility for the closure procedure and when the procedure is completed, responsibility for the local project archive. Archiving arrangements at each joint beneficiary will be communicated to the lead beneficiary and any change to the arrangements will need to be communicated to the lead beneficiary. The lead beneficiary will wait until confirmation has been obtained from WEFO before any documentation in the operation archives can be destroyed.

This process outlined above will be reviewed regularly by the project manager to ensure that everything is progressing to plan with closure.

7.13 Provide information on how you will comply with any relevant legislation relating to your operation (e.g. equality and environmental, legislation, habitats directives, Natura sites, etc.).

All the institutions to which the joint beneficiaries belong are fully cognisant of and compliant with the relevant legislation in these areas. All are deeply engaged with issues of equality and environmental sustainability and their positions are set out in Gateway 1 (Section 1.5 'Outline of Cross Cutting Themes of Equal Opportunities and Environmental Sustainability'). PPP joint beneficiaries in Ireland and Wales are, through their stakeholders, also very much aware of the protected status of certain sites in the five Port areas. Unlike many recent Interreg operations, however, PPP is focused principally on the human communities within the port towns, and its activities do not require direct intervention in or access to protected sites. Environmental issues form part of the cultural nexus of the port communities, and will have an important role to play in the creative and interpretative strands of the project, but we are not undertaking direct scientific research in these areas.

7.14 Promotional activity

7.14.1 How you will advertise and promote the opportunities / benefits that the operation is offering to target participants and/or sectors;

PPP will promote the benefits and opportunities offered by the operation throughout its lifecycle. A communication plan will be drawn up after approval during mobilization phase. Most of the project's activities involve direct engagement with local communities (the work-packages Creative Connections and the Documentary Films will see team members, artists, writers and film-crews working closely with different groups). PPP will therefore have a relatively high profile within these communities for the duration of the project and use these connections to promote the project benefits. Work-package 5, 'Community Events and Knowledge Exchange', and Work-package 6 'Communication and Dissemination' are however specifically dedicated to issues of engagement with the five Port Town communities and other interested parties, and will act to facilitate the flow of information between the beneficiaries, community organisations, local museums and local groups. Fuller details of the proposed methods to be used can be found in the delivery model outlined in Gateway 1 (Section 2.2). They will include Introductory Workshops and Day-Schools in each of the port towns in Years 1 and 4, and activities linked to the other work-packages throughout the life of the project. PPP will also have a strong and vibrant presence on social media, on its dedicated website and on YouTube. All relevant official logos will be placed on all communications, reports and posters.

7.14.2 How you will work with identified stakeholders to promote the operation

A key aim of PPP is to dovetail our activities and share our material with existing cultural and heritage-based local projects: promotion of the operation will thus occur at an organic, local level, through dozens of different channels. Conversations with potential stakeholders have already identified a number of areas where PPP activities could enhance existing local projects or help to realize new ones (examples might include: bringing new material and ideas to the community theatre group commemorating Fishguard's 1797 'Invasion'; working alongside Milford Haven Maritime Museum in their current redevelopment; collaborating at Dublin Port on plans for new museum and enhanced visitor experience). We will continue to liaise with the relevant county councils on matters of signage and the siting of new interpretation boards.

7.14.3 How you will publicise the results and impact of your operation;

The results and impact of the Operation will be publicised via the dedicated Work-package 6 (Communication and Dissemination). It will include dissemination via a project website and social media (Twitter and Instagram).

Most materials disseminated will be in bi- or tri-lingual format including websites and other publicity material aimed at the public, and where feasible ensuring that contractors and delivery partners can communicate in Welsh, Irish or English as required. The workshops, day-schools, and exhibition launches will provide further opportunities for publicising our work. Published anthologies showcasing the creative writing and artists' work and the short film documentaries will also provide more durable testimonies of the operation after it has ceased its activities.

7.14.4 How you will disseminate best practice

Best practice from this operation will be identified at the External Evaluation stage. During the delivery stage the governance meetings at central and local level will also allow us to reflect on the strengths and weaknesses of particular approaches and adapt our strategies accordingly.

7.14.5 How you will ensure that full acknowledgement of the funding from the European Union is clearly displayed including type of media utilised;

The PPP is aware that the support of the EU Funds must be publicised by all beneficiaries and that EU funding is conditional on beneficiaries taking the steps necessary to provide information to the public on the support provided by the EU. The funding agreement with the joint beneficiaries will confirm this.

The communications strategy with stakeholders and the port communities outlined above will at every stage fully acknowledge the support provided from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) by displaying the Ireland Wales programme logo and the ERDF logo (in compliance with the relevant guidance) and making explicit reference to the European Regional Development Fund. These logos will appear in a prominent position on all documentation and publicity material. Confirmation will be sought from the Communications Team at WEFO that the material complies with publicity requirements before any material is finally printed and published.

The ERDF logo will appear in colour on the PPP website along with Ireland Wales Programme logo. In addition, the lead beneficiary's website and those of joint beneficiaries will include a page (linked to the central PPP website) dedicated to the project, where all relevant logos will be visible. WEFO-approved posters will be located in prominent positions at each of the main office locations, so as to be visible to the public. Pictures will be taken to confirm compliance with this requirement and where possible pictures will be taken to confirm the use of logos at events and workshops during the life of the project etc.

Job descriptions and person specifications for new staff will include the logo and references to the source of the funding supporting the operation to ensure that applicants are aware that the posts are being part-funded by the EU. All

contractors such as the artists, writers and film-makers commissioned to work with the local communities will also receive documentation confirming that the operation is funded from EU sources.

7.14.6 How you propose to 'fly the EU flag' during the week that includes 9 May;

The lead beneficiary will liaise with WEFO at the beginning of each year to assess whether joint or separate activities should be planned. The lead beneficiary and all joint beneficiaries who have the EU flag will fly it on May the 9th above the main joint beneficiaries Institutions. Particular attention will be drawn to the benefits gained through EU funding in a blog written for the website during the week of the 9th May. Project members will take part in the broader activities organized from this week in their institutions and in the five port towns.

7.14.7 How you propose to ensure that participants and/or enterprises are clearly aware of the funding received from the EU;

All material developed for use within the operation will clearly display the relevant logos and include references to the European Regional Development Fund. Introductory speeches to public events, conferences and workshops will verbally acknowledge the EU funding source. Stands, posters, pop-up displays, presentation materials and handouts, films, books and other materials will also make it clear that the operation would not have been possible without the EU funding secured from the Ireland-Wales Programme.

7.14.8 Confirmation that you will ensure that you liaise with the JS on any proposed launches/press releases to be arranged/issued in relation to the operation;

PPP will liaise directly with the JS on the launch of the Operation and on any press releases. In addition, any promotional material or other publicly available documentation will be cleared with WEFO or other relevant authorities initially before release.

8. INDICATORS AND OUTCOMES

8.1 An analysis of the predicted longer term benefits associated with the operation.

A key aim of the PPP operation is to inform and shape the long-term heritage tourism strategies of the five port communities and their surrounding areas. PPP will achieve this through a number of key strategies and mechanisms linked to the deliverables of the project:

First, PPP will produce deliverables which are highly likely to inform regional and local tourism strategies beyond the life of the programme. This will include undertaking heritage interpretation activities which have a fairly long shelf-life, whether through the generation of permanent information boards, films, the shaping of museum displays, or other strategies.

Second, the PPP team will work closely with local stakeholders (in local authorities, local museums and heritage groups, local schools and communities) to involve them in the generation and dissemination of the port history and heritage. We expect this to generate a long-term interest amongst local groups and individuals which will hopefully empower them to explore these histories further, generating a long-term 'local' concern with the heritage of the five ports.

Third, we expect the tourism networks we set up to become self-sustaining, and we are confident that with the closure of the programme in 2023 these networks will continue to be fostered and advanced by key stakeholders (whether local chambers of commerce, local authorities, or local business leaders). We will make sure that any media associated with these tourism networks (e.g. websites) are hosted on freely accessible sites (e.g. Wordpress), and we will develop a clear strategy to minimise the risk of these failing in the future. We will also explore, at an early stage, opportunities for co-hosting the website with another organisation, such as Visit Wales, with a view to gradually transferring responsibility for the website to more locally based organisations or community groups. In providing a forum for local businesses to share experiences of tourism in the port towns, we expect new employment opportunities to emerge as the potential growth areas for port-based heritage tourism become apparent.

Fourth, we expect the wider economic benefits of the PPP operation to snowball, with the increasing popularity of Wales as a cruise destination, and the clear potential for ferry passengers to extend their stay in the port locale or to use their time in the port in different ways, especially prior to departure. The uncertainties around Brexit may actually present opportunities to explore new ways to occupy the time of passengers travelling through these ports prior to departure.

8.2 Details of the result and output indicators and their associated targets identified to be achieved in the short and medium term

The table below provides PPP's result and output indicators and their associated targets to be achieved in the short and medium term.

Indicator	Measurement unit	PPP Target (2022)	Source of data	Frequency of reporting
1. New tourism network established	Network	1 Network	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
2. Linking 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism -	Communities	5	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
3. FTEs roles created in supported enterprises	2 x FTEs	2	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
4. Equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming	Operation	Representative balance of gender, disability, ethnicity and age at all levels of staff in the operation; balanced representation of gender in all PPP heritage material	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
5. Disability	Events	DDA considerations incorporated into design of any new buildings and services relating to the operation; all events being accessible	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
6. Sustainable development	Operation	Eco Code to be developed during the mobilisation phased; operation meetings to incorporate practical environmental measures (e.g. use of Skype as far as possible); SD concerns to inform all	Operation monitoring	6-monthly

		community engagements; all commissioning to be informed by relevant SD policies.		
7. Poverty and social exclusion	Communities, Events	All events and activities to be promoted within deprived communities within the port settlements	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
8. Creative outputs in the WPs	Work packages	A series of creative artworks created to support tourism; a series of documentary films produced to encourage a greater dwell time in ports; a series of display boards produced and sited in the port communities	Operation monitoring	6-monthly

8.3 Details of the precise activities that will be undertaken during the duration of the operation in order to achieve the result and output indicators.

The precise activities to be undertaken are shown in the tables that follow in 8.5, demonstrating a clear logical flow between the planned activities, and the short and medium term result and output indicators. The table also shows who is responsible for delivery of and monitoring of each identified indicator. We also highlight the predicted longer-term benefits associated with each work package within the operation.

The PPP Operation will work through a 6-month mobilisation phase followed by a 3-year activity phase and a final 6-month closure phase. Following the mobilisation period of the operation, all three output indicators will be delivered during the delivery phase of the operation.

The mobilisation phase will consist solely of getting ready for the Operation through staff recruitment and holding planning meetings. During this period further work will be carried out to agree and sign a partnership agreement, develop a comprehensive communication plan, confirm the monitoring and evaluation requirements and agree the documentation that needs to be completed to evidence activity and compliance.

8.4 A clear logical flow should be demonstrated between the planned activities, the medium and short term indicator achievements and the longer term benefits

The WPs listed under 8.5 show how PPP will deliver the operation indicators which in turn deliver longer term benefits as described in each WP. Work packages will be managed by identified joint beneficiaries. The project GANTT chart in Annex 4 shows how the WPs are integrated within the lifecycle of the operation. The scoping process (described in the Strategic Fit section of the Business Planning Stage 1 document) involving local and national stakeholders identified six work packages to deliver the PPP operation. The functional relationships between the results and short and medium term output indicators, and the work packages that will deliver these is given in the detailed WPs in 8.5 and in the GANTT chart in Annex 4.

8.5 Details of whom will be responsible for the delivery and monitoring of each identified indicator.

The WPs below show how responsibility for delivery and monitoring of each identified indicator is assigned.

Work Package 1: Operation Management and Governance, Leader UCC, Months 7 – 48.

Predicted longer-term benefits: the creation of a team of individuals possessing extensive knowledge and experience of heritage-led development in port settlements; the creation of a template of various activities that could be used to implement the heritage-led redevelopment of port settlements elsewhere.

Operation Outputs	Objectives	Programme output indicators	Targets achieved in short/medium term	Activity	Details	Project staff	Person responsible for delivery	Person responsible for monitoring
A broad range of media planned and commissioned to encourage	Approach to procedures and procurements established	Number of coastal communities participating in cross-	Completion of PPP operation, on time and within budget.	Operation management and administration	Develop standard & compliant operating procedures for	Project manager	WP leaders (UCC, AU, UoW, WCC)	Project Manager /Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)

ge tourism to port towns		border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism			commissioning creative engagements, displays and films			
All PPP reports and monitoring documents. Deliveries against output indicators Regular progress reports Financial reports prepared. Claims submitted on 6-monthly basis.					Operation management and collection of monitoring data	Operation Manager (UCC), and team	Operation Manager (UCC)	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
					Operation governance		Steering Group, (UCC's internal	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)

							procedures)	
					Operational finance (administration for claims, auditing, etc.)		Finance Officer (UCC)	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
Progress reports	1. Cross-border collaboration between 5 port town communities		Effective collaboration between research institutions and port town communities.	Meetings of beneficiaries and steering group	Five meetings – one hosted by each beneficiary, in port towns in possible		UCC & WP leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
2 FTEs	2 new FTEs in supported enterprises		New posts created	Monitoring achievement of all outcomes	Creation of 2 new FTE posts	All	All	SRO

Work Package 2: Creative Connections, Leaders UoW & WCC, Months 7 – 40

Predicted longer-term benefits: the creation of a sustained and heightened interest in heritage in the five port settlements (among community groups and SMEs); the creation of tourism networks that will provide the basis for ongoing artistic and heritage-related collaboration between the five port settlements; the commissioning of permanent creative artworks in the five port settlements; creative artwork and community-led heritage engagement activities leading to additional time and money spent by tourists and travellers.

Output	Output indicators	Targets achieved in short/medium term	Activity	Details	Project staff	Person responsible for delivery	Person responsible for
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							monitoring
New Tourism networks established linking twinned ports.	1. Cross-border collaboration between arts groups & individuals.	1. Five port town communities involved with PPP and networking or groups & individuals.	Formation of Tourism Networks through twinning networks.	Cross-border links established between arts organisations, writers, artists etc	Project staff (UoW & WCC)	WP2 leaders (PIs UoW & WCC)	Project Manager / Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
New creative artworks produced to support tourism.	2. New creative works developed and displayed in port towns.	2. Stories and images to raise town profiles & create interest.	Call & Commissioning for defined topics on cultural heritage of port towns. Launch of PPP in each port town with SME involvement				
3. Community events & publications.	3. Community events & publications.	3. Community events undertaken and publications produced.					
5 community workshops & launches	PPP launch events	4. New promotional materials displayed.					
				Utilising new networks to develop ideas for commissioned artworks.	Project staff		

Work Package 3: Producing Documentary Films, Leader AU, Months 10 – 40.

Predicted longer-term benefits: documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports on display in the ports themselves (as part of an increased dwell time for travellers); documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports shown on ferries (to increase dwell time on future visits); documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports displayed on ferry-booking websites (allowing ferry travellers to increase the time they spend in ports);

documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports on display on cruise websites/ships (promoting bespoke walking tours of the heritage of the port settlements).

Output	Output indicators	Targets achieved in short/medium term	Activity	Details	Project staff	Person responsible for delivery	Person responsible for monitoring
5 new non-fiction films to encourage tourism	<p>1. Develop themes & topics for films using archive film footage where appropriate.</p> <p>2. Provide some content for, commission and advise on 5 films.</p> <p>3. Monitor progress and advise as necessary.</p> <p>Use process to deepen understanding of rich history and heritage of port towns & crossings.</p> <p>Increased cooperation and information exchange between stakeholders in both regions and across regions.</p>	<p>HEI & community organisations incorporate ideas into development plans for the films.</p> <p>Films commissioned & produced.</p> <p>Film screenings on ferries, port terminals & community venues.</p>	Producing documentary films utilising academic & local knowledge of sea crossings.	Develop ideas for films with a focus on the ports and the interaction between the ports to promote tourism and engage local communities.	Staff (AU)	WP3 leader (AU)	Project Manager/ Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
				5 Community workshops, one in each port town, with commissioned filmmakers to use community memories.	Staff (AU)		
				Commission and produce 5 short films	Clear brief provided and close oversight to ensure		

				delivery to spec and time.			

Work package 4: Bringing the Past to Life, Leaders UCC & WCC, Months 7-48.

Predicted longer-term benefits: a series of permanent display boards located in the port settlements, forming part of a heritage ‘trail’ around the port settlements; websites and other social media content established and maintained by community groups in order to promote the heritage of the port settlements; display boards and website content encouraging ferry travellers and cruise tourists to view the port settlements as tourist destinations in their own right.

Output	Output indicators	Targets achieved in short/medium term	Activity	Details	Project staff	Person responsible for delivery	Person responsible for monitoring
Increase tourism visits and spend associate with tourism in port towns.	1. Planning, commissioning & procurement of graphic display boards for location in each port town.	1. Board content developed and agreed. Boards commissioned.	Visualisation of cultural heritage via graphic displays	Utilise networks to identify suitable stories for tourism offering. New interpretation of maritime past via graphic displays of past sea crossings and history of the ports	Staff UCC & WCC	WP staff (UCC & WCC)	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
			Development of digital visualisations of port stories made available via mobile apps.	Utilise networks to identify suitable stories for tourism offering.	Staff UCC & WCC		

			Installation of graphic display boards	Display boards in each of the port towns	staff (UCC WCC)	WP4 deputy leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
			Further development of Tourism Network.	Workshops and Day-schools for all stakeholders in each port town	staff	WP4 PIs	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
			Improve historical knowledge to enable new and improved marketing for tourism.	Headings to include revolution, migration, the history of fishing, work and employment, tourism.	staff		
Improved tourist offering	Workshops completed.	New tourist initiatives developed.	Improved use of social media in development of heritage-related tourism.	Displays of different uses of social media to promote tourism.	staff	WP4 leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)

Work Package 5: Community events and knowledge exchange, UoW (CAWCS), months 24 – 48

Predicted longer-term benefits: the creation of a sustained and heightened interest in heritage in the five port settlements (among community groups and SMEs); an increased capacity within community and heritage groups to promote the heritage of port towns (tours, flyers, social media, talks etc); the creation of tourism networks that will provide the basis for ongoing artistic and heritage-related knowledge exchange between the five port settlements.

Output	Output indicators	Targets achieved in short/medium term	Activity	Details	Project staff	Person responsible for delivery	Person responsible for monitoring
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Improved tourist materials.	1. Cross-border collaboration between port communities 2. Improved understanding of rich port heritage amongst community.	Workshops delivered. New products developed. New ideas for promoting communities developed.	Stakeholder workshops focussing on those providing water-based activities.	Develop increased capacity in port communities to understand and disseminate good quality tourist material relating to cultural change	Staff UoW	WP3 leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
			Stakeholder Day-schools hosted by each port town community	Develop confidence and capacity	staff	WP4 leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
			Improved use of social media in development of heritage-related tourism	Displays of different uses of social media to promote tourism.	(UoW)	WP5 leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
				Ideas linked to events & activities in other workpackages	UoW	WP5 leaders	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)

				Community -of-interest values and perception s towards coastal/port features and their potential for supporting and/or augmentin g tourism	UoW	WP5 leader (UCD)	Senior Responsib le Officer (UCC)

Work Package 6: Communication and dissemination, Leader UCC, Month 7 – 48

Predicted longer-term benefits: the production of a series of policy and practitioner related outputs outlining the use of heritage-led regeneration in port communities (including ‘how to’ guides); websites on heritage-led regeneration in port settlements maintained and updated by community groups.

Output s	Output indicators	Targets achieved in short/me dium term	Activity	Details	Proj ect staff	Person respons ible for delivery	Person respons ible for monitor ing
Websites, social Media, Local & national press Exit strateg y	1. Awareness- raising initiative 2. New social media presence.	PPP outputs are dissemin ated to their target audiences .	Targeted communication/diss emination of PPP outputs. Project closure activities	Produce & deliver dissemin ation plan	UCC	PI (UCC)	Senior Respon sible Officer (AU)

developed.	Ensure all data is recorded and stored compliantly	Project successfully closed.					
				Develop PPP website, new social Media, Press coverage	RO C1 (UCC)	RO C1 (UCC)	Senior Responsible Officer (UCC)
				Implement awareness-raising initiatives	RO C1 (UCC)	RO C1 (UCC)	Senior Responsible Officer (AU)

8.6 Delivery profile

The Delivery Profile is included as Annex 3 and includes the achievement of all key activities, indicators and outcomes as identified, giving timetables for the achievement of milestones, including milestones for mobilisation and delivery. A summary of the activities to be carried out during the three-year delivery period is listed here:

Completion of mobilisation (signature of contracts, recruitment and collaborative agreement). Once mobilisation is completed and the collaborative agreement has been signed, the output indicator 'Number of research institutions (3) participating in cross border trans-national or interregional research operations' will be achieved

Development of a dedicated website

Launch of the PPP Operation

Initiation of all activity across the PPP Operation

Travelling to locations relevant for the delivery of the project activities

Activation of all work packages and their associated activities

Awareness raising events for each of the identified work package activities including workshops, catering and associated travel

Communication strategy development in conjunction with WEFO where this involves press releases or other public focusing events/notices

Meetings, which will be minuted to include:

- Operation meeting every 6 months for the whole of the PPP Operation
- Stakeholder advisory group meetings, to include members of the coastal community networks which will take place every six months. These meetings will be run in conjunction with the Operation meetings.
- Work package meetings chaired by the lead by Work package organisation
- Quarterly meetings of the UCC Monitoring Group to discuss the progress of the operation
- Quarterly meetings with the JS to discuss the progress of the operation

Workshops (including catering) for dissemination to coastal communities

Demobilisation – six months. This will include a closure process.

8.7 Monitoring and Evaluation

Internal evaluations

Data will be evaluated internally by PPP's management team and steering committee at each of the five operation meetings. Attempts will be made to process evaluation criteria, e.g. footfall in port towns, against baseline data but inevitably it will be challenging to eliminate other factors that could influence this process (BREXIT, weather conditions, ferry cancellations etc) . Where appropriate, counterfactual impact assessment will be performed by comparing indicators within the Ireland-Wales Programme area to the same indicators within similar areas which have not received programme funding to monitor trends.

External evaluations

Evaluation of the impact of project outputs and results will be assessed by an external independent contractor, and this work will be awarded via a public tender. The terms of reference of the evaluation will be in accordance with

WEFO recommendations in the “Management and Evaluation” Guidance. It is anticipated that two evaluations will take place, a midterm evaluation and a final project evaluation. In addition to considering the data recorded under outputs and results, the evaluators will particularly focus on the development of long-term impacts arising out of PPP. This will involve obtaining feedback from stakeholders/organisations involved in the collaborative projects. The final evaluation report will be disseminated to WEFO and all other stakeholders to allow the maximum amount of learning to be drawn from the project and to highlight any future actions. A more detailed monitoring and evaluation plan will be prepared during the mobilisation phase.

8.7.1 Evidence that the applicant is fully aware of their data reporting requirements in relation to the operation.

The lead beneficiary has reviewed the “Programme eligibility rules and guidance” document Version 1 (November 2015), the Ireland Wales Cooperation Programme 2014 to 2020 “Guidance on Indicator Definitions, Data and Evidence Requirements” (July 2015) and the “Claims Arrangements Instructions for Lead Beneficiaries” (January 2015) and is therefore aware of the data reporting requirements in relation to the operation and the requirements to maintain evidence of project activity and the achievement of agreed outputs. The lead beneficiary will confirm these requirements with joint beneficiaries and will confirm that each has a system in place to record and verify project expenditure and activity. The Monitoring and Evaluation Plan agreed with joint beneficiaries will describe the arrangements for monitoring the operation.

8.7.2 The applicant must demonstrate that an effective system is in place for the collection, recording and reporting of all required data

UCC as lead beneficiary will develop a process for collecting, recording and reporting all the required data and discuss this process with the PDO (Programme Development Officer). Documentation will be designed to capture the data and evidence requirements and these will be agreed prior to their introduction. The process will be reviewed by the external evaluators if required. All beneficiaries will retain all documents necessary to demonstrate that the funding rules and conditions have been met. All beneficiaries will keep appropriate and sufficient evidence to prove the proper implementation of their project and eligibility of the expenditure declared.

8.7.3 Methodology to be used to monitor and evaluate long-term benefits

Monitoring data

The first two indicators will require no specialised systems to monitor and should be evident within the delivery of the operation. The third indicator (2 new FTEs in supported enterprises) will be monitored via a stakeholder online information gathering mechanism developed within Work Package 5.

8.7.4 Baseline data

Baseline data on levels of footfall and visitor numbers will be obtained where possible and this data will be used as a baseline against which progress can be monitored and process evaluation of PPP can be undertaken.

8.7.5 Indicators outside those required by EU programmes

The CCT indicators are as described above and demonstrate the commitment of the PPP partners to gender equality and sustainability. There are no additional outputs.

8.7.6 Explanation of systems for collection, recording of monitoring data including reporting to Managing Authority and how data will be fed through into evaluation

In accordance with Priority Axis 3 of the Ireland-Wales Programme, the following monitoring data will be collected for the PPP operation:

Indicator	Measurement unit	PPP Target (2022)	Source of data	Frequency of reporting
1. New tourism network established	Network	1 Network	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
2. Linking 5 coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism -	Communities	5	Operation monitoring	6-monthly
3. 2 new FTEs in supported enterprises	2 x FTEs	2	Operation monitoring	6-monthly

A Monitoring and Evaluation Plan is included as Annex 8.

8.7.7 An explanation of how the data will be used to refine the operation and keep it on track.

There will be a continuous and systematic process of generating quantitative as well as qualitative information which will be reviewed, summarised, reported and acted upon to ensure that the operation achieves what it has set out to achieve. See also the section on Formative Evaluation below.

8.7.8 An explanation of how your systems for collecting monitoring data ensure high levels of data quality

Data quality will be checked by each of the Joint Beneficiaries to ensure that it complies with requirements as included in guidance issued the JS. Documentation that is incomplete will be referred back to the joint beneficiary for completion. UCC as lead beneficiary will meet each of the Joint Beneficiaries to discuss the requirements in detail and a requirement to maintain high levels of data quality will be included in the partnership agreement signed by all beneficiaries. All beneficiaries will be required to complete the templates provided by the JS or developed by the lead beneficiary and following approval by the JTS. The lead beneficiary will provide support if required in confirming with joint beneficiaries that data is complete.

Joint Beneficiary financial accounting records will provide detailed information about costs actually incurred and paid out, together with match funding. Each beneficiary will ensure that eligible expenditure will be capable of being linked with the corresponding activities that gave rise to those costs. For example, proof of delivery of supported activities will be traceable to the associated cost invoices and staff costs (including staff time records). This will be confirmed at local management group meetings held by each joint beneficiary. Each project will retain all documents necessary to demonstrate that the funding rules and conditions have been met.

8.7.9 Ensure that data will be effectively reported to the JS at claim periods & reviews and at other intervals, and how data will be fed through into evaluation exercises;

Joint beneficiaries will be required to report on progress using the templates provided by the JS or those developed by the lead beneficiary and following approval by the JTS. Timetables for submission of relevant information, to include draft progress reports, will be agreed with joint beneficiaries which will allow the lead beneficiary to review it for completeness and then collate the information required at operation level. Data will be gathered on an ongoing basis to confirm dissemination to a wide audience. Information will be shared with the external evaluators to enable them to evaluate the impact of the operation.

8.7.10 Collect and store wider information to be used for the management of the operation and for its evaluation.

The research data collected during PPP will consist of archival findings from institutional and community repositories (eg museums and local heritage groups). The operation already has strong connections with a variety of relevant stakeholders (see Letters of Support presented in Gateway 1) and will involve same in relation to the management of the operation via the Stakeholder Group. Data will be reviewed regularly and used to manage the project via meetings of

the Partner Beneficiary boards, reporting to the Programme Management and Monitoring Group;

The institutions involved in the Ports operation all have clear policies on electronic archival of data relating to outputs and finance both. Research data will be stored and managed within its respective work package; while financial and contractual data will be stored separately. The operation will collect and store all relevant Operation data centrally where possible but will bear in mind that each project will be responsible for its own agreed activities organised via the Partner Beneficiary boards. Data will be stored via FAIR data principles and made public through the dissemination activity to be conducted by the Operation.

8.8 An explanation and justification of the chosen evaluation methods, covering both “Formative” evaluation (during the life of the operation) and “Summative” evaluation (at the end of the operation), including why they are appropriate to the scale and scope of your operation.

The delivery of the operation is not over 3 years and therefore an end of term external evaluation is appropriate. If the costs are greater than €25k + VAT, PPP will carry out a full tender process. If between €5 - €24,999 PPP will source 3 written quotes. There will be discussion with WEFO throughout.

Formative Evaluation

The aim of the formative evaluation will be to internally review progress against the aims and objectives included in the Business Plan. This will include a review of resource efficiency, data collection and quality. It will also review whether there is effective management and good communication between joint beneficiaries. The internal monitoring data previously gathered on an ongoing basis and summarised and reported to internal groups will be evaluated. These internal groups will have previously evaluated the data to ensure that the operation is keeping on track and is delivering on what has been agreed with the JS.

In addition to quantitative data the operation will gather qualitative data in particular in regard to the knowledge transfer and dissemination activities carried out. This will establish whether the target audience is satisfied with the way that the information has been disseminated. As there are a number of methods to be employed to disseminate the results of the operation the evaluation will establish which have been the most effective at reaching the different targets groups identified at the outset.

Summative evaluation

A final report will be produced for the operation. A tendering process will be used to select the contractor to deliver the external summative evaluation. This will consider the results of the formative evaluation and the implementation of any recommendations arising from the internal monitoring and evaluation activity to improve the management and communication within and between the joint beneficiaries. The summative evaluation will also consider the impacts of the operation and whether it has achieved its overall aims and objectives and the positive effects of the operation on the coastal communities and the partnership. The management and communication of the operation will be evaluated as well as the benefits of the cross-border partnership. Engagement of the coastal communities in the operation and their response to the dissemination activities will be evaluated

8.8.1 Details of all internal and external evaluations to be undertaken must be provided, including an associated timetable.

As well as a final evaluation, the PPP Operation will undertake continual internal monitoring and will procure an external end of Operation evaluation towards the end of the Operation as described in the GANTT chart.

Timetable for internal and external evaluations

Internal evaluations

Time	Indicators to be evaluated		
	Participating coastal communities in new network	Activities	Cooperating organisations
Sept 2019 (end of mobilisation phase)	4 (beneficiaries)	Baseline data	0
March 2020	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities	Promotion of operation. Engagement of stakeholders WP 1	9 +
September 2020	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities	WPs Creative Connections Documentary films Bringing the Past to Life	20+
March 2021	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities	As above + Community events	30+

		& knowledge exchange	
Sept 2021	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities	As above + Communication and dissemination	35+
March 2020	As above	As above	
Sept 2022	As above	As above	

External evaluations

Time	Indicators to be evaluated		
	Coastal community participants in new network	Inclusion initiatives	Cooperating organisations
March 2021 (mid-term)	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities + other stakeholder organisations	Contacts with target groups Events and participation Activities and participation	30+
Feb 2023 (final)	4 (beneficiaries) + 5 coastal communities + 35 + other stakeholders	Full range of operation activities	35+

Other outputs for mid and end of operation evaluation (to be developed further during mobilisation):

- A broad range of media utilised to encourage tourists to spend time in port towns.
- Creative outputs which engage tourists with the cultural heritage of the coastal communities
- 2x new FTEs in supported enterprises

8.8.2 Dissemination plans for evaluations

The findings of all internal and external evaluations will be shared with members of the Ireland Wales JS. Where evaluations produce evidence that the operation is having a positive impact, these findings will be disseminated more widely, via

the stakeholder network, social media and the operation web site. Such information will also be shared with Fáilte Ireland and Visit Wales as well as County Councils in the areas.

9. VALUE FOR MONEY

9.1 The detailed cost benefit analysis of the short listed options listed under the Delivery criterion. This analysis should clearly identify why the preferred option was chosen and have been based on a comparison of the following factors:

As introduced in the “Consideration of Delivery Options” section, a qualitative and quantitative financial assessment was made of the preferred and “do nothing” options. In accordance with the Treasury Green Book and Capital Investment Manual, the “Do Nothing” case and a higher level containment suite have been considered as benchmarks for potential value for money.

OPTION A: Do nothing

Description

The Green Book from HM Treasury requires a ‘do nothing’ option as a base case against which to evaluate the alternative option. Under the ***Do Nothing*** option, the partners would not develop and deliver the operation.

Advantages

- There would be no call on public funds.
- There would also be no call on Universities' staff time.
- Reduced risk for the partners.

Disadvantages

- The opportunity for additional investments in the port towns and beneficial collaboration with stakeholders would be lost, and **future economic growth** for the area would not benefit from increased tourist activity.
- If there was no **new interregional network established**, the port towns would not benefit from cross-fertilisation of ideas for encouraging tourist footfall and spend and the ability to develop new products and services and influence a culture change in entrepreneurial activity would be severely limited.
- **New media** designed to interest tourists would not be developed and nor would the **new artworks**, films apps etc depriving the port towns of the opportunity to significantly improve their offerings for tourists.
- **Two new FTEs** in supported enterprises would not be established.
- No investment in **engaging and empowering the communities** of the port towns would leave them more vulnerable to economic downturns, such as may result from BREXIT.
- It would not impact on the **WG's priorities** in the area of tackling poverty and supporting disadvantaged and potentially marginalised communities.

Conclusion

The 'Do Nothing' option would **pose no significant risk to public funds**, but **would not deliver** the objectives of the project, including the opportunity to make real improvements in the 5 port towns to create and protect jobs and to increase productivity. It would also limit the future developments in the region and impact negatively on job creation potential.

OPTION B: Develop and Deliver PPP through sub-contracts

Description

This option would involve sub-contracting all the activity through procurement.

Advantages

1. Would enable a wide cross-section of individuals and businesses to contribute.
2. It might create jobs and promote economic growth.
3. It would have some of the advantages of Option C.

Disadvantages

1. Additional costs would be involved in the specification, procurement and ongoing management and oversight requirements.
2. Does not take advantage of the complementary skills and strengths of the partner institutions.
3. This option could prove very unpopular with the local community and with those businesses that the project seeks to involve as it could fail to fully engage with the port town communities and produce materials that are not welcomed.
4. There is a danger that the operation could become fragmented into several small projects and lack overall cohesion.
5. It would be more difficult to establish the new interregional network if partners are not working directly in the port towns.

OPTION C: Develop PPP through a mixture of partner activities with some procured services for specific items such as the creation of short films or commissioned artworks.

Description

This option would involve significant input by members of the PPP team particularly in understanding the different characters and needs of the 5 port towns and gaining the support and trust of the port communities. New artworks etc would be commissioned through a procurement exercise (where required) but the specification would require community input.

Advantages

1. Enables a broad range of input but with strategic oversight.
2. It would utilise the skills and expertise of the partners.
3. It would enable academics from the partner HEIs to contribute specialist knowledge both on the histories/cultures of the areas and on the opportunities for economic regeneration.

4. It builds upon other, recent investments and collaborations and thereby increases capacity and expertise.
5. It supports the priorities of Welsh Government in relation to tackling poverty and addressing the disadvantages of potentially marginalised communities.
6. It would reassure the community that research institutions have relevance for them.
7. It will enable progress to be made into increasing tourist numbers amongst those businesses that depend on visitors for their livelihood.
8. It may lever in further investments and collaborative research opportunities thereby benefitting the regional economy.

Disadvantages

1. The partner organisations are located at a distance from the port towns and may present as 'outsiders'.
2. It increases the University's financial risk.
3. It places additional demands onto staff.

Conclusion

The do nothing option would do nothing to improve visitor numbers in the port towns or their ability to benefit from new cross-border networks, reducing the potential to develop new products and services.

It would also continue to expose the port communities to the risks of marginalisation and exclusion.

Society's expectations from Universities are changing fast. There is a need to ramp up enterprising activity within their regions including collaborative, capacity building work and to identify individual strategies and bespoke solutions to particular problems.

Whilst Option A would pose **no risk to public funds**, it **would not deliver** the objectives of the project, including that of ensuring that existing expertise and collaborative research is driven into impact for the widest possible benefit. Whilst continuing to maintain the status quo, it would not create capacity or new jobs, and would therefore not support the development of the port towns. It would also not provide the maximum opportunity to develop skills, create networks, build resilience or drive economic growth.

Option B would provide similar benefits to that of Option C but with increased risks and potentially higher operational costs and without evidence of advantage or additional benefits.

Option C would allow the partners to make use of their complementary expertise to enhance the commercial opportunities within the port towns for the benefit of

the region and assist the communities to develop new jobs, facilities, skills, tools and techniques. It would also utilise sub-contracting for bespoke products and this would raise interest in and the profile of the port towns amongst a wider audience. The key issue is to raise the confidence of those living in the towns to compete in new emerging markets and potentially develop alternative niche tourist sectors to increase footfall and spend.

Option C, the desirable option, is a viable proposition that creates the opportunity to deliver the operation successfully through close engagement with the communities to generate greater and sustained visitor numbers. While there is a level of risk, this has been assessed as low and can be minimised through careful management, monitoring and evaluation.

9.2 Operation Costs

9.2.1 A detailed breakdown of operation costs linked to all identified activities & indicators. These need to be fully cross-referenced with the Delivery Profile.

All costs for the PP Operation have been carefully assessed and where possible reduced. All management costs will be kept to a minimum by using Skype, phone, e-mail or text rather than travel where possible. Consumables, the conference, workshops, etc., have all been assessed to maximise understanding and dissemination of knowledge about cultural heritage in the ports areas.

9.2.2 A cash flow projection for the lifespan of the operation identifying the cash surplus or deficit. This should include the expenditure and income on a monthly basis for the first two years of the operation, quarterly or annually beyond this

A 3 monthly cash flow has been forecast for the duration of the PPP Operation. This has been given in the delivery profile.

9.2.3 Where the cash flow indicates an overdraft or access to working capital is needed, the proof that this exists should be evidenced.

The cash flow projection demonstrates that a cash flow will not be required.

9.2.4 The assumptions used and their sources, including the methodology used to calculate (allocate and apportion) costs and income.

The salary rates used for the Welsh partners reflect the standardised rates applied throughout the Higher Education sector in the UK, through the Higher Education Role Analysis (HERA). Within Ireland, University College Cork and Wexford County Council use salary scales that are standardised rates for the public sector in Ireland.

Institutional rates and allowances, including those for mileage and daily subsistence, have been applied. Goods and services will be purchased through framework agreements, where available, and formal tendering processes will be followed for higher value items, such as the external evaluation. All procurement will be in line with local, national and European procurement regulations.

9.2.5 Indirect Costs – where the simplified cost option is not being utilised you will need to provide a robust methodology for the calculation of these costs.

The PPP operation will be using the Simplified cost option of 15% of staff costs as a Priority 3 operation.

9.2.6 Full details of any credit arrangements and facilities.

No credit arrangements will be required.

10. Further Financial Criterion: Long Term Sustainability

10.1 A detailed assessment of the potential for sustainability upon cessation of the financial support (if applicable and the activity will still be required).

The potential for sustainability upon cessation of financial support derives from the operation's Objective *to sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets in increasing visitor numbers to coastal communities of the programme area*. PPP will enable local communities to deliver memorable visitor experiences. We have already built relationships with key stakeholders including community heritage groups and on cessation of financial support, to have established self-sustaining community groups in each port town who have it in their own interests to continue generating and maintaining products and activities derived from an enhanced understanding of their own history and culture.

The three-year public-facing period of the project presents an opportunity for intensive seeding and rooting of ideas and projects, creating the conditions for continuing engagement with the past. In practical terms, PPP will explore opportunities for co-hosting the website with other organisations and will also seek to transfer responsibility for that and the Tourism Network to another organisation or community group where practicable.

The project will also lead to continuing collaborations, as the universities involved as beneficiary institutions will wish to maintain and develop academic and 'outreach' projects deriving from the PPP programme. In practical terms, such continuing and mutually beneficial relationships could involve annual lectures, talks to schools and FE Colleges as well as local historical societies and other groups. They could also involve working together to bring in new funding from different sources: for example, Milford Haven and Pembroke Dock port authority are currently helping Milford Museum prepare a bid to the Heritage Lottery Fund to fund a Development Officer at the museum. We would envisage our PPP Project Co-ordinators working closely with this person to develop future projects of benefit to the whole port area.

Discussions with the Port Heritage Director of Dublin Port, Lar Joye have proved fruitful in terms of planning for project legacy. As noted in Gateway 1, Dublin Port are the most advanced of the ports in terms of existing work on cultural heritage. They have appointed a full-time museum professional and have plans for a new museum to be located at the site of Dublin port (a building has been identified). Preliminary discussions with the Port Heritage Director suggest that the museum could house a retrospective display of outcomes and achievements of the Ports operation. Throughout the operation, research findings will feed into the development of new infrastructural plans for Dublin port, including a cycle/greenway around the port. Similar discussions with maritime heritage

groups at Rosslare Harbour, Pembroke Dock, Holyhead and Fishguard also suggest the possibility of housing small retrospective displays.

Such possibilities will be explored during the final year of PPP.

10.2 An analysis as to whether the operation has the potential to alter the delivery model in the future to a more financially sustainable model. If not, how will the activity continue to be delivered?

The delivery model involves a funded three-year period of intensive public education and the raising of awareness about local history and cultural heritage. As outlined in 10.1 above, this will result in a number of tangible legacies which will continue to realise the operation objectives after the cessation of financial support. These will provide materials and models for further development generated and delivered by the communities themselves. An ongoing and mutually beneficial relationship with the beneficiary institutions will also provide support.

10.3 If further financial support will be required, details of any plans to secure further ongoing support.

Further funding for the PPP operation will not be needed.

Where opportunities arise from collaboration with local groups to create further projects involving similar activities relating to the maritime heritage of other coastal communities on the Irish Sea, further funding can be sought from the EU (where this is possible following Brexit), UK and Irish research councils, as well as from charitable funding agencies such as the Heritage Lottery Fund.

10.4 If the activity will no longer be required, details on how the closure of the operation will be managed effectively.

The closure of the PPP operation will be managed in accordance with the regulations and guidance of UCC, the PDO and WEFO. Activities derived from the work of the operation will continue in the ways outlined above.

